

Ride for your Rights!

It's time to (ex)change your life

Project Report Summer 2011

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Europae – Student Council

Preface

Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life has its basis in the Student Council of the European University Foundation – Campus Europae. The project's vision and goals are therefore closely linked to

Campus Europae's core objective, which is the creation of a European Higher Education Area that allows each student to "experience the unique quality of a Europe whose major achievements include the Declaration of Human Rights and scientific universalism". Additionally, the project hopes "to foster the notion 'unity in diversity' and make students aware of a European identity" (Campus Europae Concept, December 2002).

Living in Europe places young people in a very peculiar position. Prospects are both rewarding and daunting at once. On the one hand, European citizenship opens up immense opportunities in the job market, travelling has never been as economical and accessible to a young generation, our rights are protected by European law, our existence dignified by the Human Rights Declaration and our generation has been spared from genocide and war thus far with the exception of the Balkans.

On the other hand, European citizenship implicates new and challenging responsibilities. If we are to believe that society is the result of our actions and that we write European history as we grow older, and if we are to believe that we are the architects of our own Europe, then we must assure that we, as the next leading generation, acquire a mindset that allows us to think of ourselves as one people. Thus, it becomes our task to monitor Human Rights violations on our continent and act accordingly. It is our task to secure the ideology of the founding fathers of Europe and to counteract any adverse effects potentially caused by fascist movements or the fear of losing our comfort and wealth when faced with a financial crisis. If we are to feel as Europeans, then we must ensure that a person's thinking capacity does neither halt at national borders, nor at the border of the Balkans or at the former Iron Curtain. Europe, after all, is what its citizens live and experience and not what we are made to believe. Without creating space and time for the young generation to foster mutual understanding, there will be no common consensus and no common European society.

Enhancing Student Mobility is one to strengthen cross-border relations and understanding and as a consequence thereof, boosting a European identity.

Knowing that Ride for your Rights! has created a community which strongly believes in the content of our Manifesto, proves to me and my colleagues that our vision can transform itself into reality with combined efforts. H.G. Wells once said: “When I see an adult on a bicycle, I do not despair for the future of the human race.” I strongly believe in H.G. Wells’s words and we strongly believe in what we ride for.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Julian Walkowiak', written in a cursive style.

Julian Walkowiak

Student Council President - Campus Europae

Initiator of Ride for your Rights!

Acknowledgments

The authors of this report would like to thank the European University Foundation – Campus Europae (EUF-CE) for sponsoring the core team of *Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life* and thus enabling a successful realisation of the project.

Further would we like to thank the EUF-CE partner universities University of Novi Sad, University of Vienna, Technical University of Łódź, University of Łódź, European Humanities University, Vytautas Magnus University, University of Latvia, Tallinn University of Technology and the University of Eastern Finland for their support and for providing the tour's participant with food and board upon arrival.

We would like to express our appreciation towards the Erasmus Student Network for collaborating with us in this project. We would like to thank all respective ESN sections and their universities for their logistical support and sponsoring.

Special thanks to Reinhard Theifert and his students of the Project Management seminar at the University of Vienna for consulting and organisation.

We warmly thank the companies Gocycle for the sponsorship of our 'Bike of Honour', Autohaus Weintritt for providing us with our support car and Ciclopia for a discount on bicycle equipment.

We wish to thank the European Students' Union, Associazione New Deal, Pannonian Association and Fraternité2020 for their ideological support and especially the Austrian National Union of Students for their financial contribution as well.

We would also like to say a big thank you to La Cafetera Roja for composing the *Ride for your Rights!* song for us and to FairSoul and VDUvideo for helping us with filming and editing work.

Last but not least, we owe our thanks to all our celebrity supporters and all remaining partners and sponsors that are listed according to countries at the end of this report.

Executive summary

This report summarises the project's concept and mission; reports on the project's major happenings; lists all *Ride for your Rights!* supporters in detail; gives a chronological overview of all events and bodies involved at each of the stops; reflects upon the impact it has caused and to what extent the goals have been achieved. It further gives the reader an insight into future plans and follow-up projects. This report was not written to serve as an assessment paper for internal use.

Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life was realised with the help of 180 volunteers from Serbia, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia, Austria, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Russia, Portugal, Italy, Germany, France and institutional support from all our partners.

The European University Foundation - Campus Europae provided the Organisation Committee with the necessary budget. The Erasmus Student Network acted as an equal partner in the project and shared responsibilities in promotion, logistical support, political lobbying and the well being of our participants.

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1. The Organising Committee

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Hungary, Austria and the
Czech Republic

2. Mission

Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life was initiated by the Student Council of Campus Europae to highlight the current shortcomings in academic European exchange programmes for students in Higher Education.

Our mission was to implement an awareness-raising project which would attract the attention of key figures and decision makers in the field of Higher Education. We aimed at engaging in lively discussions with education experts, administrative bodies and rectorates of Higher Education Institutions, European institutions and role models of society.

We focused on commenting on all current obstacles to student mobility while allowing for constructive dialogue in order to find tangible solutions as outlined in our Manifesto.

3. Manifesto

The heart of *Ride for your Rights!* is its Manifesto. It calls upon politicians, rectors, economic agents, and the society at large to work together for furthering support for student mobility. Once we have collected enough signatures, we will present it to the European Parliament. The Manifesto is currently available in 17 languages on our website.

Manifesto for more support and less obstacles for student mobility

Addressed to: EU Parliament, EU commission, National governments and all European Universities

Dear students and fellow Europeans,

Education is the most potent answer to bring about a tolerant and respectful society. Europe's future relies on citizens who will respect human rights and banish prejudice, hatred, and racism. It is imperative to enable the continent's youth to experience Europe in all its beauty and diversity.

Meeting people with different cultural backgrounds and staying in their home countries encourages tolerance, respect, and understanding. The Human Rights Declaration (§26, par. 2) states that education shall promote "understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups" it is thus necessary to develop student mobility into an integral element of our educational systems so that young people will learn not only about economics, literature or sciences but also - and just as importantly - about each other's thoughts, values and traditions.

We believe that student mobility is thus a fundamental element in assuring the sustainability of the European project and of European societies as a whole. There needs to be time and space to gain a practical understanding of Europe's core values, which in turn will empower young people to find a common European identity.

In 1999, 27 European Ministers of Education signed the Bologna declaration and created the European Higher Education Area to increase border-crossing mobility and employability. Meanwhile, there are 47 countries participating in the Bologna process. Twelve years after its implementation a great deal has been achieved in changing degree structures and furthering Europe's capacity to compete for overseas fee-paying students, but the student mobility has not received the boost many would have expected, neither quantitatively nor qualitatively. Student mobility is still reserved to only a handful of students, remains socially selective, and those who had the chance to study abroad for a semester or a year still face recognition and replacement problems after the exchange period.

Today, neither political nor geographical boundaries exist any longer in the EU. It is about time for all activists and those responsible to tear down all socio-economic barriers that hinder the achieving and surpassing the objective of having 20% of all European students become mobile no later than 2020.

We therefore call upon politicians, rectors, economic agents, and the society at large to work together for furthering support for student mobility!

- National Governments and the European Commission must rethink the financing of mobility: available grants are locked into national structures that do not account for the imbalance in the demand for mobility across the continent nor take the difference of living costs in its fullest consideration. Grant mechanisms should be made more flexible and they must not, under any circumstance, privilege shorter stay instead of longer and more exchanges.
- Higher Education Institutions must take more institutional responsibility for furthering mobility, notably as far as curricular design is concerned. Flexible curricular pathways lend themselves to studies abroad much more than strictly and densely packaged curricula. A European Code of Best Practices on course design could further the adoption of "mobility windows" and enable the establishment of a threshold of optional courses.
- The European Commission and the European Parliament must put more emphasis on the quality of credit mobility, notably with respect to recognition. A positive step would be to appoint an Ombudsman able and willing to take legal action to defend students whose Learning Agreements have not been fully respected.

Campus Europae Student Council

Erasmus Student Network

4. The concept

The project was based on three pillars: active citizenship, strengthening European values and media visibility.

4.1. Active citizenship

Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life gave students the chance to become agents of active citizenship. The project enabled people to share their first hand experiences regarding student mobility and voice their concerns in front of national and European education experts. Students could either participate in the bicycle tour itself and speak up at our various meetings, or show their support by signing our Manifesto.

4.2. Strengthening European values

Educational activities during the bicycle trip, such as workshops and study visits with a focus on European values, underlined the importance of intercultural dialogue and experience in our European society.

4.3. Media visibility

The impact of the project was interrelated with our visibility in the media. We aimed at presenting the core idea of our Manifesto not only to students and educational institutions, but also to society at large.

5. What we did

In brief, in summer 2011 over a hundred people from 18 different nations climbed on their bicycles and took part in our 5000 km journey from the Balkans to Russia. Day after day, we cycled across the continent to deliver the message of our Manifesto in 12 different countries. We met with students, rectors and education experts, and discussed all the obstacles to student mobility. We met with politicians and outstanding citizens, organised workshops, held public events, and gathered public support for a faster European integration via Student Mobility.

We visited various cultural and historical sites, and experienced Europe in its rich diversity. *Ride for your Rights! It's time to exchange your life* has quickly turned from a project, nominated for the Charlemagne Youth Prize 2011, into a large community and network of people who share interests in the fields of education, Human Rights, travelling, cycling, environmental questions and activism. Since the founding of *Ride for your Rights!* we established over 130 co-operations with clubs, communities and institutions who all share our goals and ideals. We are looking forward to form new partnerships and embrace new challenges, as active European citizens.

5.1. The route

Our route stretched itself from the Balkans to the Russian Federation. All in all, we covered 5000 km on our bicycles in a total of 74 days. We commenced our trip on the 3rd of July 2011 in Novi Sad, Serbia and arrived in St. Petersburg, Russia in the evening of the 14th of September 2011. We passed through the following countries: Serbia, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia, Austria, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland and Russia.

In order to see a detailed list of our stops, please proceed to chapter 10.

5.2. Meetings with national, European and institutional authorities

Our meetings with authorities ranged from being received by Richard Kühnel - Head of the Representation of the European Commission in Vienna, to meetings with numerous mayors, university rectors and agencies specialising in education development. The meetings catered for two important actions.

Firstly, we presented the content of our Manifesto and urged our interlocutor to implement necessary measures for improving and enhancing student mobility. Secondly, we asked them to support our project publicly by either signing the Bike of Honour, the Manifesto, sending us an endorsement letter or recording a video message for all viewers and followers of the tour.

For a detailed list of our 58 distinguished supporters with whom we have established contact or met with during our tour, please take a look at Appendix 1: Ride for your Rights! - Supporters.

5.3. Workshops

Educational workshops played a pivotal role in the project. Our workshops were realised in co-operation with local organisations and institutions of our target countries. Our workshops focused on topics that we considered relevant for fostering an attitude and mindset among our participants that would stimulate each individual to live as an active citizen in society. Topics such as Human Rights, Non-violent Action, European Citizenship and Cross-border relations all convey values which the founders of *Ride for your Rights!* strongly believe in.

5.4. Study visits

The history of Europe was highlighted with our various study visits. By visiting places like Auschwitz and the Łódź Ghetto in Poland or the 9th Fort in Kaunas, Lithuania our participants were stimulated to reflect upon the atrocities of our shared recent history.

For the full list of workshops and study visits please look at Appendix 2: Ride for your Rights! - Workshops and study visits.

5.5. Ride for your Rights! - City rides

Based on the idea of the critical mass movement, we organised our own city rides often in co-operation with local cycling activists. The city rides served as small events for local residents who could not partake in our tour but also wanted to support our cause. The city rides gave us extra visibility as it was commonly police escorted and followed by our back up van. On average, we attracted an extra 20-30 local activists and cyclists who joined our city tours. Such events allowed us to distribute promotional materials to passers-by who showed interest in our project and often the local media took the opportunity to interview us on the spot. City rides took place in the following venues: Bratislava, Vienna, Katowice, Łódź, Warsaw, and Białystok.

5.6. City tours

At all major stops our local organisers and partners arranged city tours for our participants to promote their country's culture and history.

For a detailed list of city tours and our guides please take a look at chapter 10.

5.7. Charity event Vienna

On the 21st of July 2011, we organised a charity event in Vienna called “Soli-Ride + Fest”. Thanks to live concerts performed by Ost in Translation and Sympathy for Strawberry, we managed to raise 300 EUR which were given to the “Radstromprojekt” realised by the Lastenradkollektiv Vienna. The “Radstromprojekt” is the construction of a bicycle with which electricity can be produced by manpower.

5.8. Youth in Action

After the Summer tour was finished, a final project meeting took place in Luxembourg and Brussels from the 12th to the 16th of October 2011; it brought together over 50 students from 13 different countries to discuss and evaluate the results of the bike tour. This meeting took up many of the topics discussed during the tour and widened the focus by integrating other aspects, such as the promotion of a positive attitude and awareness towards other cultures, the acquisition of competences and social skills for the social development of young people in the volunteering framework and raising awareness towards green challenges and Human Rights.

Please have a look at Annex: Youth in Action booklet for an overview of our post tour meeting.

6. Extraordinary encounters

Besides our multi-faceted programmes in each city, there were three encounters before, during, and after the tour, which deserve extra mentioning.

6.1. Hildegard Goss-Mayr

In Vienna we met with three-time nominee for the Nobel Peace Prize most and life-long Human Rights advocate – Ms. Hildegard Goss-Mayr before the tour embarked. Ms. Goss-Mayr made herself available for an interview, which you can watch on our YouTube channel and was to lead the workshop on Non-violent Action in Vienna on July 20th, 2011 in co-operation with our partners IFOR Austria.

6.2. Representatives of disabled students

On July 19th 2011, all participants of the tour met with a delegation of disabled students in front of the UN headquarters in Vienna. At this occasion we adopted the declaration and postulation of disabled students to our own Manifesto with the plea to promote the rights of disadvantaged groups as well. Please have a look at Appendix 3: *Wiener Erklärung Studierender mit Behinderungen in Österreich* (in German) and Appendix 4: *Forderung des VÖGS für barrierefreies Studieren* (in German) to read the full-length statements.

6.3. Camila Vallejo

At our final closing conference at the European Parliament in Brussels on October 19th 2011, we had a meeting with Camila Vallejo, who is the leader of the Chilean student movement and agreed on conducting a solidarity campaign called “I ride for Chile”. You will find more news on this campaign on our blog.

7. Bike of Honour

The Bike of Honour represents modern student mobility at its best. As a bike it is a symbol for mobility as such. The built in electric motor however, expresses the urgent need for an extra boost for student mobility. Therefore, the Bike of Honour accompanied us on our mission through Europe. Once on the road, the Bike of Honour served as a symbol for international co-operation. The frame of the bicycle was signed by a total of 27 distinguished personalities. By the act of riding and signing the Bike of Honour, its signatories officially supported the content of the Ride for your Rights! – Manifesto. While the Manifesto was mainly signed by students from all over Europe, the Bike of Honour attracted the attention of authorities such as the former President of the European Parliament, Ministers for Education and Science and many university rectors. The act of embellishing the Bike of Honour with autographs by most respected personae was mostly preceded by a discussion round with students who participated in the project. First-hand exchange experiences were shared and all obstacles that hinder students from studying abroad were outlined. Our proposals for improvements, as stated in the Manifesto, were explained and stakeholders were urged to implement the necessary tools which will enhance student mobility as fast as possible.

The Bike of Honour can therefore be seen as a transnational mutual agreement between decision makers and stakeholders of Student Mobility in Higher Education to eliminate remaining impediments for student exchange programmes.

Please have a look at Appendix 5: Bike of Honour Signatories to see who has signed its frame.

8. Achievements

Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life was an awareness raising project. Our goals were to draw attention to the obstacles to Student Mobility, to find supporters for our Manifesto and to suggest solutions to decision-making bodies and individuals. Assessing the impact of the project against our initial intentions, *Ride for your Rights!* was a great success:

- Our official website has over 17.500 visits (as of January 2012)
- We created a large network on Facebook with over 1000 fans (as of January 2012)
- We were visible on national TV and in newspapers in 14 different countries and collected 95 post project media references (please refer to Appendix 6: *Media Coordinator report* for details)
- We have produced a series of short video clips about the project (available on our website and our YouTube channel)
- We collected the support of 58 distinguished personalities ranging from Olympic Champions to Human Rights advocates, from Ministers for Education and Research to university rectors and from Mayors to Presidents
- Over a hundred people were actively cycling for our cause
- We organised a total of 8 workshops and seminars during the tour
- We conducted 10 study visits during the tour
- We established over 130 co-operations with NGOs, institutions, associations and communities
- A song for the project was composed by the renowned band La Cafetera Roja
- The Bike of Honour will be exhibited at the European Parliament and the Council of Europe in May 2012

9. Awards and grants

- *Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life* was nominated for the national European Charlemagne Youth Prize 2011 (national winner Austria)
- The project was taken under the auspices of the Secretary General of the Council of Europe Mr Thorbjørn Jagland
- Nominated for the annual award for “Best contribution in student representation” (Gada ieguldījums studentu pārstāvniecībā) at the University of Latvia
- The project was awarded with a *Youth in Action* grant for our final closing conference on October 12-16, 2011

10. Programme

10.1. Serbia

03-07-2011	Novi Sad – Bačka Palanka
Events	Opening Ceremony in front of townhall
Public speakers	Rector of the University of Novi Sad Miroslav Vesković City Counselor for Youth and Sports Aleksandar Kravić Vice-President of the EUF – Campus Europae Wojciech Wolf <i>Ride for your Rights!</i> Initiator Julian Walkowiak “Ideas on Tour” - Xavier König and Nanond Nopparat
Bike of Honour signed by	Rector of the University of Novi Sad Miroslav Vesković City Counselor for Youth and Sports Aleksandar Kravić
Partners and sponsors	University of Novi Sad State of Exit Foundation Hostel Milkaza Municipality of Novi Sad “Ideas on Tour” Elementary school Desanka Maksimović
04-07-2011	Bačka Palanka - Vukovar
Events	Meeting with Chair of the Bačka Palanka City Assembly Miroslav Rodić and Head of Social Activities Department of Bačka Palanka Nebojša Kuzmanović City tour given by Youth Club of Bačka Palanka and Youth Office of the Municipality of Bačka Palanka
Manifesto signed by	Chair of the Bačka Palanka City Assembly Miroslav Rodić Head of Social Activities Department of Bačka Palanka Nebojša Kuzmanović
Partners and sponsors	Youth Office of the Municipality of Bačka Palanka Youth Club of Bačka Palanka

10.2. Croatia

05-07-2011	Vukovar - Osijek
Events	Study visit to the bombed water tower memorial (Vukovar) City tour given by Pannonian Challenge (Osijek)
Partners and sponsors	Municipality of Osijek Pannonian Challenge
06-07-2011	Osijek - Mohács
Events	Visit to the Lega-Lega bike store
Partners and sponsors	Pannonian Challenge Lega-Lega Bike my day

10.3. Hungary

07-07-2011	Mohács - Pécs
08-07-2011	Pécs
Events	City tour
Partners and sponsors	Velosophie - Cultural LABOR Social Cooperation
09-07-2011	Pécs - Szekszárd
Partners and sponsors	Szekszárd Police Judo Club
10-07-2011	Szekszárd - Dunaújváros
Partners and sponsors	Elementary School Dunaújváros

11-07-2011	Dunaújváros - Budapest
12-07-2011	Budapest
Events	City tour
Partners and sponsors	ESN Hungary Corvinus University
13-07-2011	Budapest - Esztergom
Events	City tour
14-07-2011	Esztergom - Komárom
Events	Meeting with Vice-mayor Turi Bálint City tour of Komárom and Komárno
Partners and sponsors	Komárom Municipality, Komárom Secondary School
15-07-2011	Komárom - Győr
Events	Workshop on Student Exchange - Erasmus, Campus Europae, credit recognition (PRIME)
Partners and sponsors	Széchenyi István Egyetem University EGG / ESN Győr Eurodesk Hungary Mobilitás
16-07-2011	Győr
Events	City tour given by EGG / ESN Győr
Partners and sponsors	EGG / ESN Győr

10.4. Slovakia

17-07-2011	Győr - Bratislava
Partners and sponsors	ESN Comenius University (Bratislava)

18-07-2011	Bratislava
Events	City tour given by ESN Comenius University Meeting with Director of Higher Education from the Slovak Ministry of Education Peter Plavčan City ride with local activists from Critical Mass
Bike of Honour signed by	Director of Higher Education from the Slovak Ministry of Education Peter Plavčan
Partners and sponsors	ESN Comenius University (Bratislava)

10.5. Austria

19-07-2011	Bratislava - Vienna
Events	Meeting with disabled students and representatives of VÖGS (Association for deaf students in Austria) in front of UN headquarters Vienna, Resolution written by disabled students adopted to our Manifesto Welcome at premises of University of Vienna by head of the Disability Services Department of the University of Vienna Ms Birgit Virtbauer (Student Point)
Partners and sponsors	MEININGER Austrian Students' Union VÖGS University of Vienna ESN Vienna

20-07-2011	Vienna
Events	Reception at the House of the European Union and discussion with Head of the Representation of the European Commission in Vienna Richard Kühnel Workshop on Non-violent Action in co-operation with IFOR Austria Workshop on Global Education (Dr. Neda Forghani-Arani, University of Vienna) Meeting with Mr Gottfried Bacher from the Austrian Federal Ministry of Science and Research
Bike of Honour signed by	Head of the Representation of the European Commission in Vienna Richard Kühnel
Manifesto signed by	Mr Gottfried Bacher, from the Austrian Federal Ministry of Science and Research
Partners and sponsors	MEININGER IFOR Austria House of the European Union Vienna FairSoul Ciclopia Federal Ministry of Science and Research ESN Vienna

21-07-2011	Vienna
Events	City tour Solidarity Ride (Ride for your Rights! – City ride) for “Radstromprojekt” Live concerts at Tüwi with Ost in Translation, Sympathy for Strawberry
Partners and sponsors	MEININGER Tüwi Ride Club Ost in Translation Sympathy for Strawberry Vienna Bikekitchen

22-07-2011	Vienna – Laa an der Thaya
Events	Reception at the Austrian National Agency (ÖAD) Meeting with Mayor of Laa an der Thaya Manfred Fass Visit to the thermal bath Therme Laa
Bike of Honour signed by	Head of National Agency LLP Ernst Gesslbauer Mayor of Laa an der Thaya Manfred Fass
Partners and sponsors	Austrian National Agency (ÖAD) Municipality of Laa an der Thaya Therme Laa

10.6. Czech Republic

23-07-2011	Laa an der Thaya - Brno
Partners and sponsors	ISC Masaryk University ISC VUT
24-07-2011	Brno
Events	Meeting with ISC section member, on the topic of Student Mobility City tour given by ISC
Partners and sponsors	Masaryk University ISC Masaryk University ISC VUT
25-07-2011	Brno - Olomouc
Events	Meeting with Vice-mayor Jana Bohuňovská at the City Hall of Brno
Manifesto signed by	Vice-mayor Jana Bohuňovská
Partners and sponsors	ISC Masaryk University ISC VUT ESN UP Olomouc

26-07-2011 **Olomouc - Potštát**

Events	Meeting with Vice-Rector for International Relations Jakub Dürr and with the head of the International Relations Office Yvona Vyhnánková at the Palacký University Meeting with Mayor of Olomouc Martin Novotný City tour given by Municipality of Olomouc
Bike of Honour signed by	Mayor of Olomouc Martin Novotný Vice-Rector Palacký University Jakub Dürr
Partners and sponsors	Municipality of Olomouc Palacký University ESN UP Olomouc Elementary School Potštát

27-07-2011 **Potštát - Ostrava**

Events	City tour given by ISC OU Ostrava
Partners and sponsors	University of Ostrava ISC OU Ostrava

28-07-2011 **Ostrava**

Partners and sponsors	University of Ostrava ISC OU Ostrava
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10.7. Poland

29-07-2011 **Ostrava - Katowice**

Partners and sponsors	Karol Adamiecki University of Economics of Katowice ESN UE Katowice
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30-07-2011	Katowice / Auschwitz
Events	Study visit to Auschwitz City tour given by ESN UE Katowice
Partners and sponsors	Karol Adamiecki University of Economics of Katowice ESN UE Katowice
31-07-2011	Katowice - Częstochowa
01-08-2011	Częstochowa – Piotrków Trybunalski
02-08-2011	Piotrków Trybunalski - Łódź
Events	Meeting with Vice-Rector of the University of Łódź Zofia Wysokińska Meeting with Vice-Rector of the Technical University of Łódź Wojciech Wolf
Partners and sponsors	University of Łódź ESN UL Łódź ESN Eye Łódź
03-08-2011	Łódź
Events	Reception in City Hall by Vice Mayor of Łódź Agnieszka Nowak City tour given by Municipality of Łódź Study visit: Łódź Ghetto <i>Ride for your Rights!</i> - City ride
Partners and sponsors	University of Łódź Technical University of Łódź Municipality of Łódź Fundacja Normalne Miasto Łódź Cycle Chick ESN UL Łódź ESN Eye Łódź

04-08-2011	Łódź - Skierniewice
Events	Study visit: Lagiewniki Woods, WW1 graveyard
Partners and sponsors	ESN UL Łódź ESN Eye Łódź Special Needs School Skierniewice
05-08-2011	Skierniewice - Warszawa
Partners and sponsors	ESN UW Warsaw
06-08-2011	Warszawa
Events	Study visit: The Warsaw Uprising Museum Uprising Museum Jubilee critical mass ride participation <i>Ride for your Rights!</i> - City ride City tour given by ESN UW Warsaw
Partners and sponsors	ESN UW Warsaw
07-08-2011	Warszawa - Łochów
08-08-2011	Łochów – Wysokie Mazowieckie
09-08-2011	Wysokie Mazowieckie - Białystok
Events	Reception by Mayor Tadeusz Truskolawski upon arrival on city square
Partners and sponsors	Podlaskie Voivodeship Municipality of Białystok Białystok Technical University ESN PB Białystok

10-08-2011 **Białystok**

Events	Study visit: Army Museum in Białystok Ride for your Rights! - City ride City tour given by ESN PB Białystok
Partners and sponsors	Podlaskie Voivodeship Municipality of Białystok Białystok Technical University University of Białystok Medical University of Białystok Stanislaw Staszic College of Public Administration in Białystok The University of Finance and Management in Białystok Higher School of Economics in Białystok ESN PB Białystok Rio Wellness Club Army Museum in Białystok Kopiluwak Galeria Biała

11-08-2011 **Białystok – Dąbrowa Białostocka**

Partners and sponsors	Podlaskie Voivodeship Municipality of Białystok ESN PB Białystok
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12-08-2011 **Dąbrowa Białostocka - Giby**

13-08-2011 **Giby**

10.8. Lithuania

14-08-2011 **Giby - Alytus**

15-08-2011	Alytus - Vilnius
Partners and sponsors	Human Rights House Vilnius
16-08-2011	Vilnius
Events	City tour given by ESN Vilnius University
Partners and sponsors	Human Rights House Vilnius Vilnius University European Humanities University ESN Vilnius University Malsena Rokiškio pienas
17-08-2011	Vilnius
Events	Human Rights in co-operation with <i>In Actio</i> and the Human Rights House Vilnius Meeting with the Director of the Belarus Office of the Konrad Adenauer Foundation City tour given by ESN Vilnius University
Partners and sponsors	Human Rights House Vilnius Vilnius University European Humanities University In Actio Konrad Adenauer Foundation ESN Vilnius University Malsena Rokiškio pienas
18-08-2011	Vilnius - Kaišiadorys

19-08-2011	Kaišiadorys - Kaunas
Events	Public event: Welcoming by Vice Mayor Povilas Mačiulis and by City Council Member Irena Matijošaitienė, Vice Rector of Vytautas Magnus University Auksė Balčytienė and by the Academic Club of Political Scientists of VMU in Liberty Avenue City tour given by VMU Student Council
Manifesto signed by	Vice Rector of Vytautas Magnus University Auksė Balčytienė City Council Member Irena Matijošaitienė
Partners and sponsors	Vytautas Magnus University Municipality of Kaunas Academic Club of Political Scientists VMU VMU Student Council
20-08-2011	Kaunas
Events	Workshop: European Citizenship Study visit: 9th Fort Reception at the VMU Guest House
Bike of Honour signed by	Vice Mayor of Kaunas Povilas Mačiulis PhD lecturer at Vytautas Magnus University Džiugas Dvarionas Vytautas Magnus University lecturer Andrius Švarplys PhD researcher and lecturer at Vytautas Magnus University Tomas Kavaliauskas
Partners and sponsors	Vytautas Magnus University Municipality of Kaunas Academic Club of Political Scientists VMU VMU Student Council
21-08-2011	Kaunas - Labunava
22-08-2011	Labunava - Baisogala
Partners and sponsors	Baisogala Secondary School

23-08-2011	Baisogala - Šiauliai
Events	Meeting with Šiauliai City Council Member Aurimas Nausėda
Partners and sponsors	Šiauliai University ESN ŠU
24-08-2011	Šiauliai - Jelgava
Events	Meeting with International Relations staff at Šiauliai University Study visit: Hill of Crosses
Partners and sponsors	Šiauliai University ESN ŠU Latvian University of Agriculture (LLU) Student Parliament LLU Student Council LLU

10.9. Latvia

25-08-2011	Jelgava - Rīga
Events	Meeting with International Office staff and member of the LLU Student Parliament to discuss student mobility City tour of Jelgava given by Student Council LLU City tour given by ESN Rīga Kayaking
Partners and sponsors	Latvian University of Agriculture (LLU) Student Parliament LLU Student Council LLU University of Latvia Student Council of the Faculty of Education, Psychology and Art Student Council of the University of Latvia Student Union of the University of Latvia ESN Rīga Lūzumpunkts Kārums

26-08-2011	Rīga
Events	<p>Welcome by Faculty of Education, Psychology and Art Student Parliament, ESN Rīga and the President of the LU Student Union</p> <p>Discussion forum on student mobility with Jānis Vētra, Director of the Council of Higher Education, Juris Krūmiņš, Vice-Rector of the University of Latvia, Gita Rēvalde, Director of the Dept of Higher Education from the Ministry of Education and Science and Baiba Ramiņa, Head of the Academic Information Center</p> <p>Workshop: Cultural Diversity in the Baltics with UL lecturer Inese Runce at the House of the European Union</p> <p>Study visit: Sun Museum</p>
Bike of Honour signed by	<p>Gita Rēvalde - Director, Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Science Republic of Latvia</p> <p>Juris Krūmiņš - Vice - Rector, University of Latvia</p> <p>Jānis Vētra - Director of the Council of Higher Education</p> <p>Baiba Ramiņa - Head of the Academic Information Centre</p>
Manifesto signed by	<p>Gita Rēvalde - Director, Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Science Republic of Latvia</p> <p>Juris Krūmiņš - Vice - Rector, University of Latvia</p> <p>Jānis Vētra - Director of the Council of Higher Education</p> <p>Baiba Ramiņa - Head of the Academic Information Centre</p>
Partners and sponsors	<p>University of Latvia</p> <p>Student Council of the Faculty of Education, Psychology and Art</p> <p>Student Council of the University of Latvia</p> <p>ESN Rīga</p> <p>Student Union of the University of Latvia</p> <p>House of the European Union</p> <p>Sun Museum</p> <p>Kārums</p>
27-08-2011	Rīga - Saulkrasti
Events	<p>Study visit: Bicycle Museum Saulkrasti</p>
28-08-2011	Saulkrasti - Salacgrīva
Partners and sponsors	<p>Salacgrīva Secondary School</p>

10.10. Estonia

29-08-2011

Salacgrīva - Pärnu

30-08-2011

Pärnu - Järvakandi

31-08-2011

Järvakandi - Tallinn

Partners and sponsors

Tallinn University of Technology
ESN Tallinn
Student Council of TSEBA

01-09-2011

Tallinn

Events

Meeting with Vice-Rector Kalle Tammemäe and International Office staff of Tallinn University of Technology
City tour given by ESN Tallinn

Bike of Honour signed by

Vice-Rector Kalle Tammemäe of Tallinn University of Technology

Partners and sponsors

Tallinn University of Technology
ESN Tallinn
Student Council of TSEBA

10.11. Finland

02-09-2011

Tallinn - Helsinki

Events

City tour

03-09-2011

Helsinki - Lahti

Partners and sponsors

Lahti Primary School

04-09-2011	Lahti - Hartola
Partners and sponsors	Hartola Congregation
05-09-2011	Hartola - Pieksämäki
Partners and sponsors	Diaconia University Diaconia University Student Union
06-09-2011	Pieksämäki - Kuopio
Events	Meeting with Sari Raassina, Chairman of the Kuopio City Board, and Prof Kalervo Väänänen, Academic Rector of the University of Eastern Finland
Bike of Honour signed by	Sari Raassina, Chairman of the Kuopio City Board Prof Kalervo Väänänen, Academic Rector of the University of Eastern Finland
Manifesto signed by	Sari Raassina, Chairman of the Kuopio City Board Prof Kalervo Väänänen, Academic Rector of the University of Eastern Finland
Partners and sponsors	University of Eastern Finland Kuopio International Students Association
07-09-2011	Kuopio - Tuusjärvi
08-09-2011	Tuusjärvi - Joensuu
Events	Meeting with representatives of the Regional Council of North Karelia, Joensuu City Council and University of Eastern Finland Visit to UEF Student Union City tour given by ESN Joensuu
Partners and sponsors	University of Eastern Finland Regional Council of North Karelia Joensuu City Council ESN Joensuu UEF Student Union

09-09-2011	Joensuu
Events	Workshop: Cross-border seminar in co-operation with the Regional Council of North Karelia and the University of Eastern Finland Meeting and discussion with Perttu Vartiainen – Rector of University of Eastern Finland Tour to UEF Faculty of Science
Bike of Honour signed by	Perttu Vartiainen – Rector of University of Eastern Finland
Partners and sponsors	University of Eastern Finland Regional Council of North Karelia Joensuu City Council VERA Centre for Russia and Border Studies ESN Joensuu UEF Student Union

10-09-2011	Joensuu - Savonlinna
Partners and sponsors	University of Eastern Finland

11-09-2011	Savonlinna - Imatra
Partners and sponsors	Koskis Youth Club

10.12. Russia

12-09-2011	Imatra - Vyborg
Partners and sponsors	Ellipsis Fixed Gear Workshop

13-09-2011	Vyborg - Zelenogorsk
Partners and sponsors	Ellipsis Fixed Gear Workshop

14-09-2011	Zelenogorsk – St Petersburg
Partners and sponsors	Ellipsis Fixed Gear Workshop

15-09-2011

St Petersburg

Events

Workshop: Student Participation in co-operation with the Saint Petersburg Higher School of Economics, Independent Student Union of Philology Faculty SPbU, Centre for German and European Studies, Deutsch-Russischer Austausch

City tour given by Ellipsis Fixed Gear Workshop

Bike of Honour signed by

Tatiana Tsueva - Director Advisor, Higher School of Economics

Partners and sponsors

Saint Petersburg Higher School of Economics

Independent Student Union of Philology Faculty SPbU

Centre for German and European Studies

Deutsch-Russischer Austausch

Friends Forever

Ellipsis Fixed Gear Workshop

11. Future plans

As change does not happen over night and the project was widely perceived as a successful initiative, we plan to continue our work by organising 2 follow-up projects in 2012. One tour shall take place from Luxembourg to Brussels from May 25th to June 2nd 2012, and another tour shall bring the idea of *Ride for your Rights!* to the south west of Europe focusing on the topic of 'communities' in summer 2012. In 2013, we want to follow parts of the Iron Curtain Trail and ride from Berlin to Istanbul.

It is also our wish to solidify the work of our project by founding our own NGO in 2012.

12. Contact

Website: www.rideforyourrights.org

Blog: rideforyourrights.blogspot.com

Facebook: www.facebook.com/RideforyourRights

YouTube:

<http://www.youtube.com/user/RideForYourRights>

Email: contact@rideforyourrights.org

European University Foundation – Campus Europae

Chateau de Munsbach

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Luxembourg

Fax: +352 26 15 10 32

Tel: +352 26 15 10

www.campuseuropae.org

13. Appendices

13.1. Appendix 1: Ride for your Rights! – Supporters

A list of distinguished individuals who voiced their support for *Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life*

European Institutions

Jerzy Buzek	President of the European Parliament (July 2009 – January 2012)
Thorbjørn Jagland	Secretary General of the Council of Europe
Doris Pack	Chair of the Committee on Culture and Education, European Parliament
Richard Kühnel	Head of the Representation of the European Commission in Vienna

National governments

Karlheinz Töchterle	Austrian Federal Minister of Science and Research
Henry Tesch	Minister for Education, Science and Culture, Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania, Germany
Germain Dondelinger	Coordinator of the Ministry of culture, higher education and research, Luxembourg
Gita Rēvalde	Director, Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Science, Republic of Latvia
Gottfried Bacher	EU Higher Education Programmes and Bologna Process, Austrian Federal Ministry of Science and Research
Peter Plavčan	Director of Higher Education from the Slovak Ministry of Education
Egidijus Vareikis	Member of the Lithuanian Seimas (Parliament)

Regional and local government

Manfred Fass	Mayor of Laa an der Thaya (Austria)
Martin Novotný	Mayor of Olomouc (Czech Republic)
Tadeusz Truskolawski	Mayor of Białystok (Poland)
Pentti Hyttinen	Region Mayor of North Karelia (Finland)
Povilas Mačiulis	Vice Mayor of Kaunas (Lithuania)
Agnieszka Nowak	Vice Mayor of Łódź (Poland)
Marcin Krupa	Vice Mayor of Katowice (Poland)
Jana Bohuňovská	Vice Mayor of Brno (Czech Republic)
Turi Bálint	Vice Mayor of Komárom (Hungary)
Sari Raassina	Chairman of City Board, Kuopio (Finland)
Aleksandar Kravić	City counselor for youth and sports, Novi Sad (Serbia)
Miroslav Rodić	Chair of the Bačka Palanka City Assembly (Serbia)
Nebojša Kuzmanović	Head of Social Activities Department of Bačka Palanka (Serbia)
Aurimas Nausėda	Šiauliai City Council Member (Lithuania)
Irena Matijošaitienė	Kaunas City Council Member (Lithuania)

Higher Education Institutions

Perttu Vartiainen	Rector, University of Eastern Finland (Finland)
Włodzimierz Nykiel	Rector, University of Łódź (Poland)
Miroslav Vesković	Rector, University of Novi Sad (Serbia)
Kalervo Väänänen	Academic Rector, University of Eastern Finland (Finland)
Jakub Dürr	Vice - Rector, Palacky University Olomouc (Czech Republic)
Auksė Balčytienė	Vice - Rector, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)
Zofia Wysokińska	Vice - Rector, University of Łódź (Poland)
Wojciech Wolf	Vice - Rector, Technical University Łódź (Poland)
Kalle Tammemäe	Vice - Rector, Tallinn Technical University (Estonia)
Juris Krūmiņš	Vice - Rector, University of Latvia, (Latvia)
Tatiana Tsueva	Director Advisor, Higher School of Economics (Russia)
Ernst Gesslbauer	Head of the National Agency LLP, OeAD (Austria)
Jānis Vētra	Director of the Council of Higher Education (Latvia)
Baiba Ramaņa	Head of the Academic Information Centre (Latvia)

Academics

Christoph Ehmann	Secretary-General of the European University Foundation - Campus Europae (Germany)
Noel Whelan	former Vice-President of the University of Limerick and former President of the Board of Directors of the European University Foundation – Campus Europae (Ireland)
Džiugas Dvarionas	Associate Professor, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)
Tomas Kavaliauskas	PhD researcher and lecturer, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)
Andrius Švarplys	Lecturer, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)
Reinhard Theifert	Lecturer at the University of Vienna (Austria)
Neda Forghani-Arani	Lecturer at the University of Vienna (Austria)

Human Rights advocates

Hildegard Goss-Mayr	Honorary President of the International Fellowship of Reconciliation (Austria)
Stefan Malerius	Director of the Konrad Adenauer Foundation Belarus (Germany)
Anna Gerasimova	Director of the Human Rights House Vilnius (Lithuania)

Athletes

Māris Štrombergs	Olympic BMX champion (Latvia)
Raimonds Bergmanis	Olympic athlete (Latvia)
Dragan Jaćimović	Serbian alpinist (Serbia)
Iya Traore	Guinness World Book of Record holder, Football free stycler (France)
Mindaugas Kuzminskas	Professional Basketball player BC Žalgiris (Lithuania)

13.2. Appendix 2: Workshops and study visits

13.2.1. Workshops

GYŐR - Student Exchange - Erasmus, Campus Europae, credit recognition (PRIME)

(16.07.2011)

Speaker: Attila Boros

Topic: Mobility in the region of Győr

Organisation: Eurodesk Hungary

VIENNA - Global Education

(20.07.2011)

Speaker: Neda Forghani-Arani (Dr.)

Topic: Global Education

Organisation: University of Vienna

VIENNA - Non-violent Action

(20.07.2011)

Speaker: Harold Otto

Topic: Non-violent Action

Organisation: International Fellowship of Reconciliation – Austria

VILNIUS - Human Rights Education

(17.08.2011)

Speaker: Anna Gerasimova (Director of the Human Rights House)

Topic: Human Rights

Organisation: Human Rights House

Speaker: Jolita Bečienė (Projects coordinator)

Topic: What are Human Rights

Organisation: Culture center *In Actio*

Speaker: Stefan Malerius (Director of the Konrad Adenauer Stiftung)

Topic: Human Rights in Belarus

Organisation: Konrad Adenauer Foundation

KAUNAS – European Citizenship

(20.08.2011)

Speaker: Džiugas Dvarionas

Topic: European Citizenship

Organisation: Vytautas Magnus University

Speaker: Andrius Švarplys

Topic: European Citizenship

Organisation: Vytautas Magnus University

Speaker: Tomas Kavaliauskas

Topic: European Citizenship

Organisation: Vytautas Magnus University

RĪGA - Cultural Diversity and Minorities. Baltics

(26.08.2011)

Speaker: Inese Runce

Topic: Cultural Diversity and Minorities. Baltics

Organisation: University of Latvia

JOENSUU - Cross-border seminar

(09.09.2011)

Speaker: Heikki Eskelinen (Professor)

Topic: On the Edge of the Neighbourhood

Organisation: University of Eastern Finland, Karelian Institute

Speaker: Minna Piipponen (Head of Education)

Topic: VERA Centre for Russia and Border Studies - Research and Education in the UEF

Organisation: University of Eastern Finland, Karelian Institute

Speaker: Olga Davydova and Pirjo Pöllänen (Researchers)

Topic: Border and Gender

Organisation: University of Eastern Finland, Karelian Institute

Speaker: Tiina Moisala (Planner)

Topic: Cross-Border Cooperation with Russia

Organisation: Regional Council of North Karelia

Speaker: Ulla Äänismaa (Project Manager)

Topic: Cooperation between Eastern Border Regions

Organisation: Regional Council of North Karelia

ST. PETERSBURG - Student participation

(15.09.2011)

Speaker: Christoph Ehmann (Secretary General UEF-CE, Honorary Professor at Phillips University in Marburg)

Topic: Student participation in civil society and Higher Education

Organisation: European University Foundation – Campus Europae

Speaker: Yelena Belokurova (Deputy Director)

Topic: Project management as a means of implementation of student projects

Organisation: Center for Germany and Europe studies

Speaker: Viktor Vorobyov (Head of the Independent Student Union)

Topic: Critics and self-organization at the University: protest initiatives as a means of protection of students' rights

Organisation: Independent Student Union of Philology Faculty SpbSU

Speaker: Aigulle Sembaeva (Coordinator of Internship and volunteer programmes)

Topic: European voluntary service

Organisation: Deutsch-Russischer Austausch

Speaker: Tatiana Tsueva (Director Advisor)

Topic: Student projects in action

Organisation: Higher School of Economics

13.2.2. Study visits

VUKOVAR – Visit of bombed water tower

KATOWICE – Visit to National Museum Auschwitz-Birkenau

ŁÓDŹ – Visit to Łódź Ghetto

SKIERNIEWICE – Lagiewniki Woods, WW1 graveyard

WARSAW – Visit to Warsaw Uprising Museum

BIAŁYSTOK – Visit to War Museum

KAUNAS – 9th Fort

ŠIAULIAI – Hill of crosses

RĪGA – Visit to Sun Museum

SAULKRASTI - Bicycle Museum Saulkrasti

13.3. Appendix 3: Wiener Erklärung Studierender mit Behinderungen in Österreich

WIENER ERKLÄRUNG STUDIERENDER MIT BEHINDERUNGEN IN ÖSTERREICH

Zuerst möchten wir auf zahlreiche **nationale und internationale Gesetze und Verträge** aufmerksam machen, die die Gleichstellung von behinderten und nicht behinderten Studenten festlegen, wie etwa:

- Die EU-Charta der Grundrechte
- Die UNO-Resolution über die Rechte von Menschen mit Behinderungen
- Zahlreiche nationale Verfassungen, wie etwa im Artikel 7 des österreichischen Bundes-Verfassungsgesetzes: »Niemand darf wegen seiner Behinderung benachteiligt werden«.
- Zahlreiche gesetzliche Bestimmungen wie das österreichische Bundes-Behindertengleichstellungsgesetz – BGStG und das Bundes-Behindertengleichstellungs-Begleitgesetz

Wir stellen fest, dass es im Alltag noch viele Herausforderungen für eine umfassende Gleichstellung im Studium gibt. Deshalb haben wir die folgende Erklärung verfasst:

ALLGEMEIN

Wir erwarten, dass

- **behinderten Studierenden prinzipiell der Zugang im gesamten tertiären Bildungsbereich offen steht.** Studieneinschränkungen aufgrund von Behinderungen wie etwa »erforderliche Sprech- und Stimmleistung« oder »körperlich-motorische Eignung für die Bachelorstudien zur Erlangung des Lehramtes für Volksschulen und für Sonderschulen« (Hochschul-Zulassungsverordnung – HZV des BMUKK) widersprechen dem oben erwähnten Recht auf Gleichstellung
- **Lehrende sowie unsere Studienkolleginnen und –kollegen mit unseren Behinderungen selbstverständlich umgehen können** und es **Sensibilisierungsveranstaltungen** gibt. So sollten **Gebärdensprachkurse für Studierende und Universitätsmitarbeiter kostenlos angeboten** werden
- es im Sinne der **Selbstbestimmung Persönliche Assistenz** und **ähnliche Dienstleistungen** für Menschen mit verschiedenen Behinderungen im Universitäts-Alltag gibt. Dazu gehören auch Ansprech- und Beratungsstellen, die etwa **in Gebärdensprache kommunizieren** können
- in allen Belangen, die behinderte Studierende an den Universitäten und Hochschulen betreffen, **Expertinnen und Experten in eigener Sache beigezogen** werden
- an allen Universitäten und Hochschulen **notwendige abweichende Prüfungsmethoden zugelassen** werden
- es das Recht gibt, den **behinderungsbedingten Mehraufwand erstattet zu bekommen**
- **Auslandsaufenthalte und internationale Mobilität** Menschen mit Behinderungen ebenso wie allen anderen Studierenden **prinzipiell zugänglich sind**

STUDIERENDE MIT BEWEGUNGSBEHINDERUNGEN

Wir erwarten, dass

- **die Gebäude der Universitäten und Hochschulen barrierefrei zugänglich sind.** Dies betrifft etwa Seminarräume und Hörsäle, Zimmer von Lehrenden, Bibliotheken, Aufenthaltsbereiche, WC-Anlagen, aber auch das **Mobiliar**. Zur Gleichberechtigung gehört z.B. auch, dass die Eingänge für behinderte Menschen prinzipiell die Haupteingänge sein sollen, da Nebeneingänge diskriminieren und mit Umwegen und Absonderung von anderen verbunden sind.
- **Expertinnen und Experten für barrierefreies Bauen bei sämtlichen Neu- und Umplanungen** beigezogen werden

STUDIERENDE MIT SEHBEHINDERUNGEN

Wir erwarten, dass

- alle **Webseiten und Lernplattformen der Universitäten und Hochschulen für blinde und sehbehinderte Studierende barrierefrei zugänglich** sind
- die Gebäude mit **Blindenleitsystemen, akustischen Ansagen** in den Liften etc. ausgestattet sind und adäquate **Information über die Lage von Räumen** allen blinden und sehbehinderten Studierenden zugänglich ist
- Sämtliche **Literatur**, die für das Studium benötigt wird, zugänglich ist (etwa durch Digitalisierung, vergrößerte Ausdrücke etc.)

STUDIERENDE MIT HÖRBEHINDERUNGEN¹

Wir erwarten, dass

- es barrierefreie Gebäude (Lichtsignalanlagen, Videotelefon/SMS, Induktionsanlagen...) gibt
- **Gebärdensprachdolmetschung (ÖGS), Tutoring in LVs und Mitschreibkräfte** ausreichend zur Verfügung stehen, sodass wir unser Studium **im vorgeschriebenen Zeitrahmen absolvieren können**
- dass **Lecture-Screening mit Gebärdensprachdolmetschung** zur Verfügung gestellt wird
- es Workshops zur **Einführung in die Wissenschaftssprache** gibt (**schriftlich und in ÖGS**)

STUDIERENDE MIT PSYCHISCHEN BEHINDERUNGEN

Wir erwarten, dass

- unsere **unsichtbaren Behinderungen anerkannt** werden und dass eine **Ent-Stigmatisierung von Menschen mit psychischen Behinderungen aktiv gefördert** wird
- es das **Recht auf Beurlaubung** gibt
- für uns adäquate **abweichende Prüfungsmethoden** zugelassen werden (etwa schriftliche Präsentationen statt mündlicher Referate)

STUDIERENDE MIT CHRONISCHEN KRANKHEITEN

Wir erwarten, dass

- es das **Recht auf abweichende Prüfungsmethoden und Beurlaubung** gibt

PERSONEN MIT LERNBEHINDERUNGEN

Wir erwarten, dass

- individualisierte Förderung dazu führt, dass auch **Personen mit Lernbehinderungen ihr Recht auf Bildung an Hochschulen** verwirklichen können – wie es internationale Beispiele beweisen, zumal es bereits Akademiker mit Down-Syndrom oder mit Autismus gibt.

WIEN, AM 19. JULI 2011

Diese Resolution wurde von verschiedenen Studierenden mit Behinderungen im Juli 2011 erstellt und wird von internationalen Studierenden des international und EU-weit anerkannten Projekts »Ride for Your Rights« im Zuge Ihrer Europa-Tour für die Rechte von Studierenden übernommen und nationalen sowie internationalen Stellen übergeben.

¹ Eine detailliertere Auflistung gibt es im Papier des Vereins österreichischer gehörloser Studierender (VÖGS)

13.4. Appendix 4: Forderung des VÖGS für barrierefreies Studieren

DER VÖGS¹ FORDERT

für alle schwerhörigen und gehörlosen Studierenden in Österreich Barrierefreiheit.

Konkret bedeutet dies:

- Das Behindertengleichstellungsgesetz muss im gesamten tertiären Bildungssektor in Österreich umgesetzt werden, um ein barrierefreies Studium zu ermöglichen
- DolmetscherInnen-Einsatz in Österreichischer Gebärdensprache in Lehrveranstaltungen
- SchriftdolmetscherInnen in den Lehrveranstaltungen
- Ständige TutorInnenbegleitung
- Gebärdensprachkompetente Service- und Beratungsstellen an den Unis und FHs
- Diskriminierungsfreier Zugang zur Ausbildung für alle Berufe
- Aktuelle Vorlesungsskripten sind online zu stellen

Primäre Ziele:

- DolmetscherInnen-Einsatz (ÖGS und/oder Schrift nach Wahl des Studierenden) in aller Lehrveranstaltungen, die ein gehörlose/schwerhöriger Studierender im Semester besucht
- TutorInnen (für gebärdensprachige Studierende in ÖGS und für schwerhörige Studierende in Lautsprache)
- Begleitung in den Tutorien von den LV (fachlicher Inhalt)
- Unterstützung bei wissenschaftliches Schreiben (Seminararbeiten)
- Mitschreibkräfte
- Inhaltliche Aufklärung der Mitschrift
- Etablierung einer universitäts- und fächerübergreifenden und permanenten Servicestelle, die Organisation und Bezahlungsmodalitäten von Dolmetscher sowie von Mitschreibhilfen und Tutorien übernimmt (Minimierung der Doppelbelastung).
- Permanente gebärdensprachige Beratungsstelle für gehörlose und schwerhörige Studierende (Servicezentrum) Orientierungsseminar (Ablauf Uni, Organisation, Erstellung Stundenplan, etc.) in Zusammenarbeit mit anderen studentischen Organisationen
- Freie Wahl der Prüfungsmodalität
- Diskriminierungsfreien Zugang zur Ausbildung für alle Berufe (z.B. Hörunfähigkeit darf kein Grund für Zulassungsverweigerung sein)

Sekundäre Ziele:

- Bereitstellung von ÖGS - Dolmetscher für administrative Wege, Sprechstunden mit Lehrenden, etc.

1 Verein österreichischer gehörloser Studierende

- Verlängerung der Familienbeihilfe
- Förderungsdauer ohne Altersgrenze auch bei Berufstätigkeit
- Workshops und Seminare in ÖGS (Einführung in die Wissenschaftssprache, wissenschaftliches Schreiben, wissenschaftliche Fachgebärden, etc.)
- Barrierefreie Gebäude (Lichtsignalanlagen, Videotelefon/SMS, Induktionsanlagen, ...)
- Skriptenpflicht für alle aktuellen Lehrveranstaltungen (Vorlesungsinhalt)
- Sensibilisierungsveranstaltungen für Studierende, Mitarbeiter und Lehrende
-

Mehr Informationen über den VÖGS findet man auf:

www.voegs.at

www.twitter.com/voegs

www.facebook.com/voegs.at

13.5. Appendix 5: Bike of Honour Signatories

European Institutions

Jerzy Buzek - President of the European Parliament

Doris Pack - Chair of the Committee on Culture and Education, European Parliament

Richard Kühnel - Head of the Representation of the European Commission in Vienna (Austria)

National governments

Karlheinz Töchterle - Austrian Federal Minister of Science and Research (Austria)

Germain Dondelinger - Coordinator of the Ministry of culture, higher education and research Luxembourg (Luxembourg)

Gita Rēvalde - Director, Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Science Republic of Latvia (Latvia)

Peter Plavčan - Director of Higher Education from the Slovak Ministry of Education (Slovakia)

Egidijus Vareikis - Member of the Lithuanian Seimas (Parliament) (Lithuania)

Regional and local government

Manfred Fass – Mayor of Laa an der Thaya (Austria)

Martin Novotný – Mayor of Olomouc (Czech Republic)

Povilas Mačiulis - Vice Mayor of Kaunas city (Lithuania)

Sari Raassina - Chairman of City Board, Kuopio (Finland)

Aleksandar Kravić - City counselor for youth and sports (Serbia)

Higher Education Institutions

Perttu Vartiainen – Rector of University of Eastern Finland (Finland)

Miroslav Vesković – Rector of University of Novi Sad (Serbia)

Kalervo Väänänen - Academic Rector of the University of Eastern Finland (Finland)

Jakub Dürr – Vice - Rector, Palacky University Olomouc (Czech Republic)

Zofia Wysokińska – Vice – Rector, University of Łódź (Poland)

Wojciech Wolf – Vice – Rector, Technical University of Łódź (Poland)

Kalle Tammemäe – Vice - Rector, Tallinn Technical University (Estonia)

Juris Krūmiņš - Vice – Rector, University of Latvia (Latvia)

Tatiana Tsueva - Director Advisor, Higher School of Economics St. Petersburg (Russia)

Jānis Vētra – Director of the Council of Higher Education (Latvia)

Baiba Ramiņa – Head of the Academic Information Centre (Latvia)

Academics

Džiugas Dvarionas – Associate Professor, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)

Andrius Švarplys – Lecturer, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)

Tomas Kavaliauskas – PhD researcher and lecturer, Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)

13.6. Appendix 6: Media Coordinator report

Extract of report submitted by Sviatlana Dzenisevich

Geographical coverage:

The project got media coverage in 15 different languages in over 14 countries (not taking into consideration ESN-newsletters). There were over 95 links of post-media coverage and at least 60 links of pre-project media coverage. The information about the project was evenly published both in national and local media, especially during the run of the project. The most media coverage took place in Austria, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, and Latvia. Taking into consideration the number of countries covered by the project, this could be considered as an outstanding result.

Type of media outlet and media resource:

While before the project's start the major media resources announcing the project were university and NGO websites, during the project period the major media resources were newspapers, reporting online and in print. Most of the universities reported via their own channels about the project after its start. There were at least 5 broadcastings on national and 6 on local media portals about the project (e.g. ORF, TV3, Telewizja Polska, Радио-телевизија Војводине etc.). The project was widely covered in social networks and through new media (Facebook, V Kontakte, YouTube, Vimeo, Draugiem.lv and others).

13.7. Appendix 7: Newspaper illustrations

2011.07.01 Backopalanachki Nedelnik (Serbia)

Студенти возе бицикле Европом

“Ride for your rights”! it's time to exchange your life

Пројекат “Ride for your rights, it's time to exchange your life” или „Вози за своја права, време је да утичеш на свој живот” покренут је од стране Campus Europe у сарадњи са ESN-ом. Студенти из целе Европе ће учествовати у вожњи бициклом од Новог Сада до Санкт Петербурга, пролазећи кроз још десет земаља -Хрватску, Мађарску, Словачку, Аустрију, Чешку, Пољску, Литванију, Летонију, Естонију и Финску. Овај пројекат и вожња имају за циљ да укажу на проблеме и важност мобилности студената, а такође и на то колико је важно бити активан члан друштва и шта значи би-

ти грађанин Европе. Вожња ће кренути из Новог Сада 3. јула и завршава се у Санкт Петербургу 15. септембра, који су једина два битна града на рути који нису у Европској Унији. Током вожње биће организоване разне пропратне активности. У сваком граду где је планирана дужа пауза биће организован обилазак града и споменика битних за европску историју и културу, као и састанак са представницима локалне власти и челницима универзитета, а у неким градовима ће бити одржане радионице и трибине.

Група бидиклиста и пратећи тим стижу у Бачку Паланку 3. јула у поподневним часовима, а настављају своју руту сутрадан 4. јула. Домаћини гостима у нашем граду биће представници Канцеларије за младе Општине Бачка Паланка, ученици и наставни кадар основне школе „Десанка Максимовић”, Омладински клуб и локална самоуправа. Више информација на www.rideforyourrights.org – сазнајемо од Љиљане Жижкић, организаторке посете у Бачкој Паланци.

2011.07.03 Vojvodina (Serbia)

ИЗ КАНЦЕЛАРИЈЕ ЗА МЛАДЕ

ВОЗИ ЗА СВОЈА ПРАВА

Пројекат "Ride for your rights, it's time to exchange your life" („Вози за своја права, време је да утичеш на свој живот“) покренут

вожњи бициклом од Новог Сада до Санкт Петербурга, пролазећи кроз још 10 земаља (Хрватска, Мађарска, Словачка, Аустрија, Чешка, Пољска, Литванија, Летонија, Естонија, Финска). Овај пројекат и вожња имају за циљ да укажу на проблеме и важност мобилности студената, а такође и на то колико је важно бити активан члан друштва и шта значи бити грађанин Европе. Вожња ће кренути из Новог Сада 3. јула и завршава се у Санкт Петербургу 15. септембра, који су једина два битна града на рути који нису у Европској Унији. Током вожње биће организован обилазак града и споменика битних за европску историју и културу, као и састанак са представницима локалне власти и челницима универзитета, а у неким градовима ће бити одржане радионице и трибине.

Група бициклиста и пратећи тим стижу у Бачку Паланку 3. јула у поподневним часовима, а настављају своју руту сутрадан 4. јула. Домаћини гостима у нашем граду биће представници Канцеларије за младе Општине Бачка Паланка, ученици и наставни кадар основне школе „Десанка Максимовић“, Омладински клуб и локална самоуправа. Више информација на www.rideforyourrights.org – сазнајемо од **Љиљане Жижић**, организаторке посете у Бачкој Паланци.

је од стране Campus Europae у сарадњи са ESN-ом. Студенти из целе Европе ће учествовати у организоване разне пропратне активности. У сваком граду где је планирана дужа пауза биће

2011.07.04 Blic (Serbia)

FOTOGRAFIJE: J. IVANOVIĆ

Start projekta "Ride for your rights" u Novom Sadu

Studenti iz Evrope krenuli na neobično putovanje Biciklima do Sankt Peterburga

DINKA MAKSIMOVIĆ

Studenti iz Srbije, Finske, Bugarske i Austrije krenuli su juče biciklima sa Trga slobode u vožnju do Sankt Peterburga, dugu 4.000 kilometara. Oni će putovati kroz 12 evropskih zemalja, a u svakoj će im se pridruživati kolege s drugih univerziteta. Reč je o projektu "Ride for your rights" koji treba da ukaže na probleme i važnost mobilnosti studenata, a koji organizuje Kampus Europe u saradnji sa studentskom mrežom Erasmus.

- Rekreativno vozim bicikl, planirao sam ovog leta da se zaputim na neko duže putovanje i zbog toga sam danas ovde. Mnoge moje kolege ne nameravaju da pređu ceo put

Akademci idu na put dug 4.000 kilometara, kroz 12 država, koji će trajati 75 dana

do Rusije i svih 4.000 kilometara, ali ja sam odlučio da idem do kraja. Biće to divna avantura i veliki izazov, a pošto sam u dobroj formi nadam se da neću imati poteškoća na putu. Predviđeno je da do Sankt Peterburga stignemo za 75 dana, odnosno 15. septembra. Nazad ću avionom jer zbog obaveza na fakultetu nemam vremena da se vraćam biciklom – priča Saša Marjanović, student druge godine novosadskog Fakulteta tehničkih nauka.

Tokom vožnje studenti će proći kroz Srbiju, Hrvatsku,

Mađarsku, Slovačku, Austriju, Češku, Poljsku, Litvaniju, Letoniju, Estoniju, Finsku i Rusiju. Pojedini među njima preći će ceo put, dok će se ostali priključivati turi po etapama. U raznim gradovima na maršruti održavaće se radionice, sastanci s predstavnicima lokalne vlasti, univerziteta, sa sportistima, a biće i turističkih obilaska gradova.

- Ovo je sjajno iskustvo i odlična prilika da se družimo, upoznajemo drugačije kulture i promovisemo ideju zajedništva i mobilnosti. Drago mi je što krećemo baš iz Novog

Sada, a nadam se da će put biti uzbudljiv - kaže Julijan Valkovijak, student iz Austrije i jedan od koordinatora projekta.

Svetlana Šešum, koordinatorka projekta pri Univerzitetu u Novom Sadu, kaže da je Novi Sad polazna tačka, a s Trga slobode kreće 11 studenata.

- Pored novosadskih, tu su i studneti iz Finske, Bugarske i Austrije, priključuju im se mladi iz svih zemalja kroz koje tura prolazi, a koje su i članice Kampusu Evrope. To je uzbudljiva vožnja koja razvija zdravo mlado društvo koje će primenjivati, promovisati i poštovati ljudska prava i u isto vreme postavljati osnove za slobodnu mobilnost po Evropi, bez ograničenja – kaže Šešumova.

2011.07.04 Dnevnik (Serbia)

ЈУЧЕ ИЗ НОВОГ САДА КРЕНУЛА ПАНЕВРОПСКА СТУДЕНТСКА БИЦИКЛИСТИЧКА ВОЖЊА

За мобилност без ограничења кроз 12 земаља

Паневропска бициклическа вожња студената из целе Европе почела је јуче у 11 часова испред Градске куће у Новом Саду. Од 13 студената који су кренули на ово путовање на два точка, под мотом „Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life!“, само ће **Саша Марјановић** прећи целу руту и стићи чак до Санкт Петербурга у Русији! Циљ вожње је промоција мобилности студената, охрабривање активног учешћа младих у друштву и ојачавање толерантног друштва Европе. Студенти ће бициклом обићи 12 европских земаља – Србију, Хрватску, Мађарску, Словачку, Аустрију, Чешку, Пољску, Литванију, Летонију, Естонију, Финску и Русију. Вожња ће трајати до 15. септембра.

Организатор је Campus Europa, програм размене студената у оквиру којег студенти Универзитета у Новом Саду од 2004. године имају могућ-

Фото: Р. Хашић

ност да проведу академску годину на једном од партнерских европских универзитета, док

на УНС исто тако долазе страни студенти. Чланови Студентског савета Campus Euro-

пае у сарадњи с ESN-ом (Erasmus Student Network) покрену пројекат који ће побољшати и убрзати не само развој у сфери европског образовања него и сарадњу међу младима Европе. Главна идеја овог пројекта је да се постигну заједнички циљеви који су постављени пред целокупно европско друштво – мање препрека при академским разменама и даљи подстицај на што већу мобилност студената. Овим путем се развија здраво младо друштво које ће примењивати, промовисати и поштовати људска права и, у исто време, постављати основе за слободну мобилност по Европи, без ограничења, као што је декларисано у ЕУ директивама и у Универзалној декларацији о људским правима.

Основни тим и сви заинтересовани студенати, политичари, активисти и појединци који подржавају циљ ће везити од Србије до Русије или се прикључивати тури по етапама. Током туре, у разним градовима на маршрути ће се одржавати различити догађаји, радионице, састанци с представницима локалне власти, универзитета, спортистима, као и културни и туристички обиласци града. Овај пројекат је непрофитног карактера и у организацији студената, трошкови учесника током вожње нису покривени. Смештај током туре ће бити у камповима, хостелима, салама школа, преко couch surfingа, а могуће је да ће на неким местима бити и бесплатан, у зависности од локалних организатора.

А. Ва.

Ректор испратио студенте

Уз малобројне суграђане, члан Градског већа за спорт и омладину **Александар Кравић**, ректор Универзитета у Новом Саду проф. **Мирослав Весковић** и проректор Техничког Универзитета у Лођу проф. **Војцех Вулф**, испратили су јуче 13 учесника пројекта „Ride for your rights“. Они су пожелели студентима из целе Европе који су кренули из Новог Сада до Санкт Петербурга да им путовање прође што лепше.

- Младим људима не треба пуно времена да се упознају и почну да се друже. Кључ свега је младост, и зато сматрам да овај пут има само један циљ, а то је да се млади повезују и забављају. Ипак, овај пут представља и повећање мобилно-

сти студената с универзитета на универзитет – рекао је Кравић.

Један од учесника је и **Саша Марјановић** студент друге године Факултета техничких наука у Новом Саду који је како каже решио да истраје до краја. Он ће бициклом стићи за 75 дана до Санкт Петербурга.

- Ако све буде у реду тамо би требало да стигнемо 14. септембра. Неће сви учесници ићи до краја неки иду само до Мађарске, а неки до Аустрије или Финске. Колико имам сазнања, неки студенти ће нам се прикључити у другим државама, све у свему очекујем да ово буде једно забавно и узбудљиво путовање – каже Саша. **Љ. На.**

2011.08.04 Express (Poland)

Pedałują przez Europę

MIĘDZYNARODOWA

grupa studentów przyjechała wczoraj na rowerach do Łodzi. Żacy z kilkunastu krajów Europy to uczestnicy programu wymiany między uczelniami „Campus Europae”. Należą do niego Uniwersytet Łódzki i Politechnika Łódzka. Studenci podczas dwupółmiesięcznej wyprawy rowerowej, w czasie

której przejadą ponad 4 tys. km, promują przyjazne środki transportu i walczą o stworzenie możliwości studiowania na zagranicznych uczelniach. W tej sprawie napisali manifest, pod którym zbierają podpisy.

Uczestnicy wyprawy byli już w Nowym Sadzie, Budapeszcie, Bratysławie, Wiedniu i Ostrawie. Po wyjeździe z Łodzi odwiedzą jeszcze Wilno, Kowno, Rygę, Tallin i Sankt Petersburg. (1)

FOT. PAWEŁ ŁACHETA

2011.08.04 Gazeta Wyborcza (Poland)

Manifest na rowerach. Studenci przejadą się po Europie

Dotknięcie nosa Tuwima na szczęście

•• Rowerzyści z 19 europejskich uczelni jeżdżą po całej Unii, wioząc manifest wzywający do zniesienia barier w mobilności studentów.

Dokument podpisali już czołowi politycy UE, austriacki minister edukacji i przewodniczący Parlamentu Europejskiego Jerzy Buzek. Wczoraj podpisały go łódzkie władze.

- Obecnie tylko 4 proc. studentów uczy się na studiach poza swoją macierzystą uczelnią - mówi Julian Walkowiak, studiujący na uniwersytecie w Wiedniu uczestnik rajdu. Jego zdaniem można to zmienić, jeśli uczelnie nie będą ustawiać sztywnych grafików, bo wtedy trudniej zdobywać wiedzę w innych placówkach, a władze zaczęły wspierać takie inicjatywy finansowo. - Wiadomo, że z pracą dla ludzi z zagranicy jest problem

- inny język, inne zwyczaje. Dlatego z pieniędzmi jest kłopot, gdy się chce studiować w obcym kraju - przekonuje Julian. Z tego powodu on i jego koledzy z programu wymian studenckich Campus Europae jeżdżą na rowerach po Europie, zabiegając o poparcie wpływowych polityków i rektorów uczelni. Przejechali już cztery tysiące kilometrów. Wczoraj w południe zawitali do łódzkiego urzędu miasta, gdzie ich dokument podpisała wiceprezydent Łodzi Agnieszka Nowak.

- To miasto wyrosło na współzyciu i współpracy czterech narodów, tutaj wasz manifest ma szczególne znaczenie - podkreślała pani wiceprezydent.

W Campus Europae bierze udział 21 europejskich uczelni. Z Polski są na razie tylko dwie: łódzka politechnika i uniwersytet. ●JK

2011.08.04 Polski Dziennik (Poland)

W skrócie

Przyjechali rowerami aż z Serbii

Kilkunastu studentów z 12 krajów Europy przyjechało rowerami do Łodzi. Podróżują z Nowego Sadu w Serbii do Petersburga w Rosji. W ten sposób promują ideę wymiany studenckiej między krajami w ramach programu Campus Europae. W Łodzi spotkali się z władzami miasta, Uniwersytetu Łódzkiego i Politechniki Łódzkiej. Przywieźli manifest z prośbą o ułatwienie wymiany studentów. Więcej zdjęć na www.dzienniklodzki.pl.
mt

FOT. MATYŁDA WITKOWSKA

Studenci promują wymianę między uczelniami

2011.08.09 Gazeta Wyborcza (Poland)

Rowerzyści z kilku krajów świata zjadą na białostocki rynek

POD PATRONATEM GAZETY WYBORCZEJ

•• Nie lada gratka czeka fanów dwóch kótek. Dzisiaj po południu do centrum Białegostoku wjedzie międzynarodowa rowerowa wycieczka. Każdy z białostoczian będzie mógł do cyklistów dołączyć i popedałować z nimi głównymi i ulicami miasta. A nawet dalej.

W tym międzynarodowym peletonie jedzie ponad dwadzieścia młodych osób z różnych części Europy. Rowerzyści wyruszyli na początku lipca, we wrześniu ich wyprawa dobiegnie końca - w sumie przemierzą 4 tys. kilometrów. Byli już m.in. na Węgrzech, Słowacji, w Austrii, Czechach. Obecnie przemierzają Polskę, potem skierują się na Litwę, Łotwę, Estonię, Finlandię, i tak aż do Rosji. We wtorek po południu przyjadą do Białegostoku. Pojawią się na Rynku Kościuszki, potem przejadą głównymi ulicami miasta - każdy z mieszkańców może dołączyć do tego peletonu. W dalszą drogę z Białegostoku wyjadą w czwartek. I ci, którzy chcą się do tych wojaży podłączyć, powinni skontaktować się z kierownikiem grupy. Eskapada to projekt „Ride for your Rights!” zainicjowany przez Radę Studencką Campus Europae oraz organizację Erasmus Student Network (wspiera międzynarodową wymianę studencką). ● TUU

Program międzynarodowego rajdu w Białymstoku:

wtorek (9 sierpnia)

•• **godz. 17** - planowany przyjazd uczestników rajdu

•• **godz. 17.30** - uroczyste powitanie kolarzy przez władze miasta na Rynku Kościuszki.

UWAGA! W dowolnym momencie można dołączyć do kolarzy i jechać z nimi. Tego dnia przejazd planowany jest ulicą: Kawalerską, Wiejską, Mazowiecką, Legionową, Sienkiewicza i Rynek Kościuszki.

środa (10 sierpnia)

•• **godz. 17** - debata w klubokawiarni Kopiluwak (ul. Sienkiewicza 9) - wstęp wolny

•• **godz. 18.15** - oficjalny przejazd ulicami miasta: Rynek Kościuszki, plac Jana Pawła II, Branickiego, Miłosa, św. Ojca Pio, Zwierzyniecka, Mazowiecka, Wyszyńskiego, Grunwaldzka, Krakowska, św. Rocha, Piłsudskiego, Sienkiewicza, Rynek Kościuszki.

UWAGA! Ci białostoczanie, którzy chcą dołączyć do peletonu, na Rynku Kościuszki mają się stawić o godz. 18. ●

2011.08.10 Gazeta Wyborcza (Poland)

Rowerzyści zajechali na białostocki rynek

**POD PATRONATEM
GAZETY WYBORCZEJ**

•• Z czasowym poślizgiem, trochę zmęczeni, ale zadowoleni, po południu wjechali do Białegostoku. Mowa o uczestnikach międzynarodowego rajdu „Ride for your Rights!”.

Na uczestników rowerowej eskapady na Rynku Kościuszki przy fontannie czekał m.in. wiceprezydent Białegostoku Aleksander Sosna (również miłośnik dwóch kółek) i grupa białostoczan-rowerzystów. Poza powitaniem były też gratulacje z powodu przebytej trasy. Bo uczestnicy tego rajdu mają do pokonania około 4 tys. km. Eskapadę rozpoczęli wraz z początkiem lipca od Serbii przez Chorwację, Węgry, Słowację, Austrię i Czechy. W Białymstoku będą do czwartku. Potem udadzą się na Litwę, Łotwę, Estonię, do Finlandii i dalej aż do Rosji - gdzie w połowie września zakończą wyprawę.

Międzynarodowy rajd rowerowy dotarł wczoraj do Białegostoku. Brawo!

W środę o godz. 17 w klubokawiarni Kopiluwak odbędzie się debata z uczestnikami rajdu, potem około godz. 18.15 przejadą ulicami miasta (inni rowerzyści też mogą do nich dołączyć) - rozpoczną od Rynku Kościusz-

ki i ruszą w stronę placu Jana Pawła II i ul. Branickiego.

Rajd zainicjowany został przez Radę Studencką Campus Europae oraz organizację Erasmus Student Network. ☺ TUU

2011.08.10 Poranny (Poland)

NASZ PATRONAT - Międzynarodowi studenci przyjechali z Serbii do naszego miasta na rowerach, aby promować zdrowy styl życia i studiowanie za granicą. Białostoczanie przywitani ich na Rynku Kościuszki

Uczestnicy rowerowego rajdu Ride for your Rights dotarli do Białegostoku

Grupa międzynarodowych rowerzystów dotarła wczoraj do Białegostoku. Przejechali Serbię, Chorwację, Węgry, Słowację, Austrię, Czechy i Polskę, aby propagować w tych krajach zdrowy styl życia oraz przyjazne środowisko środki transportu.

Podczas spotkań z mediami i przedstawicielami uczelni wyższych zwracają uwagę uniwersytetów, urzędów miejskich, a nawet rządów krajów na potrzebę większego wsparcia i konieczność poprawy mobilności studentów Europejskiego Obszaru Szkolnictwa Wyższego – mówi Adrian Tomaszewski, przewodniczący Erasmus Student Network Politechnika Białostocka.

Mimo złej pogody, rowerzyści zostali przywitani bardzo gorąco przez mieszkańców naszego miasta. Aby pobyt w Białymstoku nie był nudny studentom zaplanowano szereg atrakcji. Jedną z nich jest odnowa biologiczna w RIO Wellness Club. Po wypoczynku kolarze zwiedzą Muzeum Wojska. O godz. 17 wezmą udział w ogólnodostępnej debacie zorganizowanej w klubokawiarni Kopiluwak przy ul. Sienkiewicza 9. A o godz. 18 wyruszą z Rynku Kościuszki w oficjalny przejazd ulicami miasta. Każdy będzie mógł do nich dołączyć. Pojadą Placem Jana Pawła II, Branickiego, Miłosa, św. Ojca Pio, Zwierzyniecką, Mazowiecką, Wyszyńskiego, Grunwaldzką, Krakowską, św. Rocha, Piłsudskiego, Sienkiewicza i wrócą na Rynek Kościuszki.

(ADEK)

FILM: www.poranny.pl

Kolarze promują w Białymstoku sieć europejskich uniwersytetów Campus Europae oraz Ogólnoeuropejską Organizację Studencką Erasmus Student Network, które pomagają studentom w wyjazdach na studia zagranicze

2011.08.11 Poranny (Poland)

Miasto zaskoczyło rowerzystów.

Nasz patronat - Wizyta w Muzeum Wojska i Pałacu Branickich bardzo spodobała się studentom. Ci, którzy byli u nas wcześniej, nie mogli uwierzyć, że miasto mogło tak się z mienić w ciągu ostatnich czterech lat.

Adrian Kuźmiuk
akuzmiuk@poranny.pl
tel. 85 748 95 18

Chcieliśmy udowodnić, że europejska integracja jest możliwa, podobnie jak mobilność studentów – mówi Julian Walkowiak z Austrii. – W końcu nie każdy ma możliwość studiowania za granicą.

Jest jednym z uczestników rajdu Ride for your Rights, którzy z Serbii przyjechali na rowerach do Białegostoku. Międzynarodowi studenci promują tolerancję, mobilność i ideę wymian międzynarodowych w odwiedzanych miastach.

– Najtrudniej było jechać przez Węgry z powodu ekstremalnych upałów – mówi Julian. – A najbardziej stresująco w okolicach Katowic. W pewnym momencie trochę się pogubiliśmy.

Rowerzyści omijali najbardziej ruchliwe trasy. Często wybierali dłuższe, ale za to bezpieczniejsze odcinki. Najwięcej uczestników rajdu, bo aż 28 osób, jechało z Bratysławy do Wiednia. Tam wielu zrezygnowało. Jedni nie mieli czasu, inni pieniędzy, niektórzy musieli wracać do pracy.

– Ciężko było na trasie do Łodzi – mówi Julian. – Drogi były wąskie i zakorkowane przez tiry. Dopiero za Łodzią pojechaliśmy bocznymi drogami łączącymi mniejsze miejscowości. Dzięki temu mogliśmy podziwiać piękne krajobrazy.

Białystok zaskoczył rowerzystów. Jadąc tutaj mieli o nim zupełnie inne wyobrażenie. – Byłem tu cztery lata temu – mówi Tiago Simoes z Portuga-

Tiago Simoes z Portugalii (z lewej) i Julian Walkowiak z Austrii zwiedzają Białystok przy okazji rajdu Ride for your Rights

lii. – Wtedy miasto wyglądało zupełnie inaczej, szczególnie centrum. To niesamowite jak bardzo się zmieniło.

Tiago nie może uwierzyć, że zainwestowaliśmy tak wiele w renowację miasta, rozbudowę infrastruktury, naukę i badania. Chwali nas za postęp jaki osiągnęliśmy w zaledwie cztery lata.

– Władze miasta zrobiły bardzo dobrą rzecz – mówi Tiago.

– Stworzyły miejsce przyjazne mieszkańcom, z którego nie chce się wyjeżdżać i które warto odwiedzić. Wiem, jak to jest mieszkać na przedmieściach. W Portugalii ludzie zazwyczaj opuszczają miejsce, w którym dorastali. Mam też nadzieję, że potraficie wykorzystać pieniądze mądrzej niż Portugalczycy. My zmarnowaliśmy swoją szansę. Nasz rząd nie był taki sprytny, ale widzę, że w Bia-

lymstoku idzie w dobrym kierunku.

Jednak nie wszystko spodobało się rowerzystom. – Przydałoby się stworzyć więcej dróg dla rowerów, ale takich oddzielonych zupełnie od chodnika, bo jazda po waszych ścieżkach między pieszymi jest bardzo niebezpieczna – dodaje Julian.

Dzisiaj studenci-rowerzyści wyruszą w dalszą drogę. Przez kraje bałtyckie i Finlandię pojedą do Rosji.

2011.09.11 Uljas (Finland)

Ride for your Rights!

Tiedätkö, mikä on Campus Europae? Tämä kansainvälinen opiskelijavaihtojärjestö lähti tekemään itseään tunnetuksi järjestämällä pyöräilytempauksen Euroopan halki. Uljas haastatteli aiheesta Sini Makkosta. - Outi Pulliainen, teksti & Ride for your Rights!, kuva

Projektin tarkoituksena on parantaa opiskelijoiden liikkuvuutta Euroopassa.

”Monet asiat vaikeuttavat vaihtoon lähtemistä,” toteaa Sini, joka uskoo, että kampanja tulee vaikuttamaan asioihin myönteisesti.

”Eniten positiivisia ajatuksia on herännyt siitä, että pyöräily ja sen mukana ajatuksien julkituominen on hyvin ekologinen tapa saada ääni kuuluville ja herättää huomiota,” Sini kertoo.

Projekti on sujunut yli odotusten. Alunperin pienen porukan pyöräilytempaus on paisunut huomattavasti ja kerännyt huomiota myös mediassa. Opiskelijat polkevat 4000 km:n matkan Serbian Novi Stadista Venäjälle Pietariin ja kiertävät matkalla Campus Europae -kaupunkien kautta. ”Hurja matka tuo on polkupyöräillä, tätä on ihmetelty.”

Pyöräilijöiden ydinjoukko on vaihdellut 5-20 henkilön välillä. Kaupungeissa mukaan on liittynyt enemmänkin väkeä ja niin odo-

tetaan käyvän myös Suomessa.

Pyöräilijät saapuvat Kuopioon 6. syyskuuta ja suuntaavat sieltä Joensuuhun, jossa Suomen päätapahtuma järjestetään 8. ja 9. syyskuuta. Ennen Venäjälle siirtymistä pysähdytään myös Savonlinnassa.

”Vielä ehtii mukaan,” sanoo Sini.

”Venäjälle ei toki pääse ilman viisumia, mutta muuten voi ajaa lyhyemmän tai pidemmänkin matkan.”

Ja jos pyöräily ei kiinnosta, pyöräilijöille järjestetään kaupungissa erilaista ohjelmaa, johon muutkin voivat osallistua. Tiedossa on ainakin kaupunkikierroksia ja illanviettoa.

Sini kehottaa tarkastamaan tarkemmat aikataulut Facebookista osoitteesta: <http://www.facebook.com/RideforyourRights>.

Ja tietysti jokainen voi käydä allekirjoittamassa projektiin liittyvän manifestin osoitteessa <http://www.rideforyourrights.org/>.

Campus Europaesta lisää:
<http://www.campuseuropae.org/en/>

14. Annex: Youth in Action booklet

'Youth in Action' Programme

Education and Culture

Youth

Campus Europae

Programme «Jeunesse en action»

DG Éducation et culture

INTERNATIONAL EXCHANGE
ERASMUS STUDENT NETWORK

Campus Europae

Final Booklet

This booklet has been finished printing in December 2011 under the program **Youth in Action, Action 5 – Support for European Cooperation in the youth field / Sub-Action 5.1 - Meetings of young people and those responsible in the youth field.**

It has been written and designed by Silvia Crocitta, Bernd Justin Jütte, Juan Fernández Cantero and Marco Cuzzocrea on the behalf of European University Foundation – Campus Europae

A sincere thank you to everyone who participated in the bike tour and the Youth in Action project, they made it possible to happen.

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European University Foundation – Campus Europae

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Manifesto

The project (Action 5 – Support for European Cooperation in the youth field /
Sub-Action 5.1 – Meetings of young people and those responsible in the youth
field)

The bike tour idea

Aims and Objectives

The topics

The activities

Outcomes

Results

Evaluation

Partners and Participants

Free Space

INTRODUCTION

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The project "Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life!" was presented in October 2010 during the plenary meeting of the European University Foundation - Campus Europae Student Council. From the beginning it represented the commitment of the young people taking part in their communities as Student Representatives and active citizens from different European countries. The support of the promoter and partners involved in the Youth in Action grant conceded by the Luxembourg National Agency permitted to build this project step by step, making it real.

As young people what we want is being active in the daily European life and being the actors of our cooperation; we are looking forward to participate in similar initiatives and experiences in the future.

EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY FOUNDATION - CAMPUS EUROPAE

EUF-CE was created on November 2003 when representatives of the participating universities signed the Charter of European University Foundation. The foundation functions as an "umbrella" for the alliance of 18 European universities constituting Campus Europae with its main office in Munsbach, Luxembourg. The Foundation assumes the central function of coordination and support for its main activity: the enhanced, high-quality exchange of university students within the network.

On the basis of mutual trust and cooperation, it brings together universities characterised by a high degree of individual freedom of action and a strong commitment for European values. Its functioning organs are: the Administrative Board consisting of the Rectors or Legal Representatives of the member universities, represented by a Secretary General in charge of the running of the Campus Europae Secretariat.

The Student Council, consisting of one Student Representative from each member university, is a consultative organ with capacity of initiative. Other operating bodies are the Subject Committees, which coordinate academic cooperation and recognition in the respective academic disciplines, the foreign language teaching experts group, which shapes and implements the language policy and the LEP-finders (for-work placements).

RIDE FOR YOUR RIGHTS – It's time to (ex)change your life!

THE "5 W-QUESTIONS"

5

WHY

Because we pretended to call upon politicians, rectors, economic agents, and the society at large to work together for furthering support for student mobility and youth employability on the basis of active participation, volunteering, human rights, green policies and Bologna Process declaration (1999).

WHERE

The bike tour: from Novi Sad (Serbia) to St. Petersburg (Russia).

The Youth in Action implementation phase: in Luxembourg, Brussels (Belgium) and Munsbach (Luxembourg).

WHAT

The bike tour: day by day, we cycled across the continent delivering the message of our Manifesto in 12 different nations.

The Youth in Action project: we planned all the steps for the implementation of the grant; we built activities promoting the "learning by doing" method in the non-formal education framework; we developed the project; we closed the last documents to be sent to the NA in Luxembourg.

HOW

Building a young network which collaborated intensively for all the duration of the project.

WHEN

The bike tour: in summer 2011, from 7th July to 15th September.

The Youth in Action implementation phase: in autumn 2011, from 12th to 16th October.

MANIFESTO

Manifesto for more support and less obstacles for student mobility
Addressed to: EU Parliament, EU commission, National governments and all European Universities

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Dear students and fellow Europeans,

Education is the most potent answer to bring about a tolerant and respectful society. Europe's future relies on citizens who will respect human rights and banish prejudice, hatred, and racism. It is imperative to enable the continent's youth to experience Europe in all its beauty and diversity.

Meeting people with different cultural backgrounds and staying in their home countries encourages tolerance, respect, and understanding. The Human Rights Declaration (§26, par. 2) states that education shall promote "understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups" it is thus necessary to develop student mobility into an integral element of our educational systems so that young people will learn not only about economics, literature or sciences but also – and just as importantly – about each other's thoughts, values and traditions.

We believe that student mobility is thus a fundamental element in assuring the sustainability of the European project and of European societies as a whole. There needs to be time and space to gain a practical understanding of Europe's core values, which in turn will empower young people to find a common European identity.

In 1999, 27 European Ministers of Education signed the Bologna declaration and created the European Higher Education Area to increase border-crossing mobility and employability. Meanwhile, there are 47 countries participating in the Bologna process. Twelve years after its implementation a great deal has been achieved in changing degree structures and furthering Europe's capacity to compete for overseas fee-paying students, but the student mobility has not received the boost many would have expected, neither quantitatively nor qualitatively. Student mobility is still reserved to only a handful of students, remains socially selective, and those who had

the chance to study abroad for a semester or a year still face recognition and replacement problems after the exchange period.

Today, neither political nor geographical boundaries exist any longer in the EU. It is about time for all activists and those responsible to tear down all socio-economic barriers that hinder the achieving and surpassing the objective of having 20% of all European students become mobile no later than 2020.

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We therefore call upon politicians, rectors, economic agents, and the society at large to work together for furthering support for student mobility!

- National Governments and the European Commission must rethink the financing of mobility: available grants are locked into national structures that do not account for the imbalance in the demand for mobility across the continent nor take the difference of living costs in its fullest consideration. Grant mechanisms should be made more flexible and they must not, under any circumstance, privilege shorter stay instead of longer and more exchanges.
- Higher Education Institutions must take more institutional responsibility for furthering mobility, notably as far as curricular design is concerned. Flexible curricular pathways lend themselves to studies abroad much more than strictly and densely packaged curricula. A European Code of Best Practices on course design could further the adoption of "mobility windows" and enable the establishment of a threshold of optional courses.
- The European Commission and the European Parliament must put more emphasis on the quality of credit mobility, notably with respect to recognition. A positive step would be to appoint an Ombudsman able and willing to take legal action to defend students whose Learning Agreements have not been fully respected.

Campus Europae Student Council
Erasmus Student Network

THE PROJECT

(Action 5 – support for European cooperation in the youth field / Sub-action 5.1 – meetings of young people and those responsible in the youth field)

The funded activity was part of a greater project – *Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life* – organized by the European University Foundation – Campus Europae (EUFC-CE).

In summer 2011 students from different European countries embarked on a pan-European bike tour to promote and raise awareness for student rights in student mobility among young people. More as means than as ends in themselves the notions of active citizenship participation in democratic life as European citizens accompanied the main message throughout the project. Through workshops, conferences, teambuilding, short seminars and work groups during the tour young European were confronted with these diverse issues and discussed them against their different national, cultural and social backgrounds.

The final meeting took place from 12th to 16th October 2011 in Luxembourg, Munsbach and Brussels; it brought together over 50 students from 13 different countries to discuss and evaluate the results of the bike tour. This meeting took up many of the topics discussed during

the tour and widened the focus by integrating other aspects, such as the improvement of European mobility and active citizenship, the promotion of a positive attitude and awareness towards other cultures, the acquisition of competences and social skills for the social development of young people in the volunteering framework and raising awareness towards green challenges and human rights. The preparation phase included training based on the principles of informal learning and non-formal education and it was divided into 6 modules: 1) History, values and citizenship of the European Union; 2) the European institutions and citizens; 3) policies for European Mobility; 4) Knowledge of other countries (participant) and intercultural dialogue; 5) "Green" policies and pollution; 6) Human Rights.

By way of practical implementation the participants were animated to share and develop their ideas on European Mobility, European Citizenship and European Volunteering focusing on creating benefits and suggesting improvements to all the topics. Through different variations of the "learning by doing" approach, which included small project works, focus groups, reflection groups, short workshops and open debates the theoretical foundations were strengthened by concrete application.

The follow-up phase, which lasted until mid-December, served to analyze the results and communicate them to the participants as well as beyond by addressing the stakeholders of the EVF-CE, the universities involved and partner organizations.

THE BIKE TOUR IDEA

In summer 2011 over a hundred people from 18 different nations climbed on their bicycles and took part in our 5000 km journey from the Balkans to Russia. We met with students, rectors and education experts, and discussed the obstacles to Student Mobility.

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We also met with politicians and outstanding citizens, organized workshops, held public events, and gathered public support for a faster European integration via student mobility.

We visited various cultural and historical sites, and experienced Europe in its rich diversity. *Ride for your Rights! It's time to exchange your life* has quickly turned from a project nominated for the Charlemagne Youth Prize 2011 into a large community and network of people who share interests in the fields of education, Human Rights, travelling, cycling, environmental questions and activism. Since the founding of *Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life!* we established over 60 collaborations with clubs, communities and institutions who all share our goals and ideals. We are looking forward to form new partnerships and embrace new challenges for the future, as active European citizens.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The project was aimed at developing participants' awareness of Mobility and European Citizenship. For this purpose, it offered a no-risk platform to debate and active participation to young people and policy makers.

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The main objective of the project was to understand the role and expectations of the young participants regarding global, regional and local challenges; the following goals were set:

- Promote a positive awareness of young people towards the principle of active citizenship by encouraging dialogue and open debate. Young People reflected on which new approaches must be taken by the political class and the new generations to improve the mobility of European students taking as example the bike tour which has been carried out during the summer 2011.
- Follow up the existing principles developed on Mobility and Citizenship in Europe, contributing to the dissemination of good practices and to make young people sensitive for the value of a European society as a united and unique identity.
- Get participants involved in the European Year on Volunteering (2011), adopting the principles of the European year against social exclusion, increasing awareness of the value of volunteering in society, and creating a dialogue with the institutions and exchange of best practices.

In non-formal education it is important to introduce innovative methods to be developed by the 62 young people involved. The idea was to create basic and useful tools to adopt and implement in home societies.

To allow young people to contribute to the development of the task a fertile environment it was created to enhance the participants' abilities. For this reason, during the meeting young people made use of original comparison methodologies such as focus group, role playing and the study of intervention techniques, with the purpose of finding an original approach to the definition of the subject. Furthermore, young people have been involved in the workshops contents and regulations, giving them an active role in the meeting preparation.

THE TOPICS

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The entire project took advantage of the European Year on Volunteering (2011). The participants had the possibility to analyse the role of volunteers and their importance in their different realities (both local and national).

Participants acquired tools to implement the results of the project in practice and to improve and further develop their previous knowledge. For this purpose they had to contact local authorities and entities to disseminate the final results of the project according with the given indications.

Apart from the European Year of Volunteering, two more topics took special relevance during the meeting: the European Mobility and the European Citizenship; students realized the importance and advantages of mobility for young people as European individuals. Participants were meant to take an active role within their communities; in this sense some regions have been studied and analyzed to reflect on the benefits they might gain from mobility.

Linked to the 3 main topics the participants also discussed about 2 more sub-themes: Human Rights on the basis of the Bologna Process and the Manifesto created by the Student Council; green policies and environmental respect for a better future.

THE ACTIVITIES

Wednesday 12th October (Luxembourg)

The project started with a welcome conference and a 30 minutes introduction about the project, its aims and objectives and its framework. The conference was opened by the Secretary General and the Vice-President of the EVF-CE and gave an introduction on the importance of student mobility and active participation in our societies and the role of universities therein. By taking the example of "Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life!" the process of conducting a multinational project that united several aspects of mobility and citizen participation as an initiative of individuals was described and the valuable outcomes of such project for participants as well as for society in general were underlined. This introduction was followed by using the Open Space Technology to let the participants discuss and ask questions on the project.

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In the evening participants engaged in team-building activities to lay the interpersonal foundation for constructive group-work during the next days.

Thursday 13th October (Luxembourg)

European citizenship, mobility and active participation workshops:

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- Little introduction of the historical overview of the European citizenship
- Levels for future development
- Brainstorming and Open Space Technology
- Pros and cons of being active and being mobile
- Taking responsibilities for the European future
- Short interviews about the "Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life!" idea and insight overview:
 1. Importance
 2. Objectives
 3. Planning as volunteers
 4. Why taking responsibilities for our society
 5. How to respect the environment: green policies
 6. What is behind/what is beyond
- Simulations
- Reflection groups

All the activities implemented after the brainstorming were analyzed through divided group work and the "building a flipchart" method; at the end, each group shared the results and space was given for questions and open debates.

Friday 14th October (Brussels)

Visit to Brussels:

- Meeting with partners and supporters
- Visit to the European Parliament

In Brussels:

- Youth in Action Programme presentation
- Open debate about the Youth in Action Programme
- Results and ideas for the future of young initiatives taking "Ride for your Rights – It's time to (ex)change your life!" as an example to start and implement new projects
- Focus groups
- Green policies (video and open space technology)
- Reflection groups

Saturday 15th October (Munzbach)

Volunteering (morning):

17

- Introduction and energizer
- “Mandala of the perfect Volunteer” (reflection on how to be Volunteer, use of colors, flipcharts, post-its, etc.)
- Workshops lead by participants: how to be a volunteer in our nations (preparing flipcharts, presentation and short debates)

Human Rights (afternoon):

- Short seminar and open space technology
- Workshop about Human Rights
- Sharing results of the entire Youth in Action project
- Presenting results of the bike tour in relation to the Youth in Action project
- Open debate: future youth initiative and partnerships
- Closing Ceremony

OUTCOMES

The achievements we reached as direct product of the implementation phase and dissemination of the project are:

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- Having promoted a positive awareness of young people towards the principle of active citizenship by encouraging dialogue and debate; young People were enabled to reflect on which new approaches must be taken on the political level and the new generations to improve the mobility of European students, taking as example the bike tour which was carried out during the summer of 2011;
- Having followed-up the existing principles developed on Mobility and Citizenship in Europe, contributing to the dissemination of good practices and to make young people sensitive for the value of a united and unique identity for the European society;
- Having had participants involved in the European Year on Volunteering (2011), adopting the principles of the European year against social exclusion, increasing awareness of the value of volunteering in society, and creating a dialogue with the institutions and exchange of best practices;
- Having increased the dialogue and cooperation between young people and political actors in order to provide a real contribution to the creation of policies for youth participation;
- Having linked the topic of European Mobility with being an active European Citizen, fostering a positive identity in order to improve both concepts;

- Having laid the basis for establishing a European Day for Mobility (8th May) by setting a concrete example by the pan-European bike tour;
- Having laid the foundations for an objective and meaningful recognition of social inclusion of young people as a fundamental policy;
- Having developed the theme of volunteering and green policies, and then compare doses on the role and actions to promote positive attitudes to the promotion
- Having developed and promoted the value of non-formal education, assessing the value added in the field of social inclusion;
- Having enhanced the dialogue between institutions and young people, in order to promote coherent policies to real needs;
- Having encouraged young people to design and construct their own future;
- Having promoted a positive attitude towards the project meeting, encouraging the exchange of experiences, dialogue and debate on the issues;
- Having increased practical, cultural, organizational, interpersonal and social skills that contribute to the social development of young people;
- Having strengthened participants in the value of tolerance and self-acceptance;
- Having created or exploit new creative tools related to the topics;
- Having provided information about Human Rights and the can and must be respected and be made aware of.

RESULTS

The project was integrated in the wider framework of the *Ride for your Ride – It's time to (ex)change your life!* pan-European bike tour, which promoted and enhanced mobility, student rights and active European Citizenship. The meeting in Luxembourg, Brussels and Munsbach was a continuation of these efforts in that it served to concentrate and evaluate the outcomes of the tour.

The participants thus served as providers and recipients of different experiences that were shared through social media. The awareness raised throughout Europe by the project, in particular at the universities of the participants could be used to transport information about the outcomes of the project to genuine stakeholders. Such stakeholder outside the universities are located at the national and European policy and administrative level as well as in communities of different background (e.g. sports, volunteering, NGOs, green movements). The coverage of the project by outside access of offered information could be measured by access numbers of the project webpage and social network pages. A multiplying effect was reached by combining receptive participants and targeted information: participants were generally predisposed in having a positive attitude and profound interest in European topics and were thus more

inclined to believe in the purpose of the project and to participate actively and take advantage of the opportunities offered. And, at the same time, to extend their cultural boundaries, close gaps of information and by helping others to overcome intercultural/cultural obstacles and misunderstandings.

Others, certain represented among participants as well, who did not have a deep prior knowledge of the benefits of being European needed, and to that effect appreciated first-hand information and experiences. This information was by way of this project provided to all the young people, institutions, NGOs and other multiplying channels requesting for it, and the future perspective is to build new relationships, new projects, new ideas and new networks.

For a continuation of these efforts similar projects are planned to be conducted. For this purpose the Youth in Action provides an effective hub and will most certainly considered again.

Intensive follow-up and continuation of dissemination efforts is made via social networks and established online channels and institutionally by promoter and partner institutions.

EVALUATION

4 different types of evaluation have been carried out:

- daily evaluation (through reflection groups during the implementation phase)

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- mid-term evaluation (through opened questions about the implementation phase in general)
- final evaluation (final questionnaire about what the participants in general thought about the project)

- self-assessment (we decided to use the 8 key-competences recognized in the Youthpass, even if the action is not allowed an official recognition for the Youthpass)

PARTNERS AND PARTICIPANTS

Promoter: European University Foundation – Campus Europae

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Participants from Luxembourg:
Bernd Justin Jütte, Joachim
Wyssling.

Partner (in cooperation): ESN International

Participants from Belgium: Katja
Krohn, Marek Böser, Barbora
Pecivová.

Guest: Tania Berman

Partner: ESN Germany

Participants from Germany:
Johannes Trommer, Julia Höltge,
Olesya Ryabykh.

Partner: ESN Spain

Participants from Spain: Silvia
Crocitta, Juan Fernández Cantero,
Juan Colino Barrogón, Alicia
Sánchez Hernández.

Partner: ESN Italy

Participants from Italy: Marco Cuzzocrea, Michela Apruzzese, Giovanni Gerolimetto, Katia Strangis.

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Partner: ESN Austria

Participants from Austria: Julian Walkowiak, Camillo Breiling, Georg Klopf, Katarzyna Kupaj.

Partner: Academic Club of Political Science (University of Kaunas)

Partner: Belarusian Human Rights House in Exile in Vilnius

Participants from Lithuania: Indre Starazinskaite, Paulius Baltokas, Kristina Koryagina, Marta Ladutko, Iryna Lunevich, Ausra Rinkeviciute, Nastassia Salash.

Partner: ESN Łódź

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Partner: ESN EYE-Łódź

Participants from Poland: Julian Witowski, Olga Baczyk, Mateusz Hilgner, Justyna Marta Kaluzka, Pawel Kordek, Pawel Lisiewski, Sylwia Luszczek, Sara Nałaskowska, Jakub Przybylski, Marek Sokolowski.

Partner: KISA – Kuopio

International Students' Association

Participants from Finland: Eeva Asikainen, Kauppinen Eveliina, Sini Makkonen, Kai Ruotsalainen.

Partner: ESN Aveiro

Participants from Portugal: Tiago Simoes, Ana Rita Pereira Araújo, Gonçalo Ribeiro.

Partner: Students' Council –
University of Latvia

Participants from Latvia: Liga
Kuzmane, Dita Bogdane, Daiga
Kuzmane, Kaspars Mednis.

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Partner: ESN Tallin

Participants from Estonia: Sigrid
Västra, Hanna Kalajas, Märt
Mađissoon, Urmas Umborg.

Guests

**CENTAR ZA
SAMOAKTUALIZACIJU
Novi Sad (Serbia)**

Participants from Serbia: Svet Lana
Šešum, Jasna Šešum, Sasha
Marjanovic, Bogdan Skoric.

**FRIENDS
FOREVER
St. Petersburg (Russia)**

Participants from Russia: Irina
Baigozina, Dasha Dospolova, Maxim
Kapitan.

